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Master Thesis

Sedimentation of Erythrocytes in a Density Gradient of Colloidal Silica Nanoparticles

submitted by

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1 Motivation and Literature Survey

Perhaps the first documentation of a density gradient dates back to 1630 when Galileo Galilei described a floating ball of wax in a diffusion gradient between phases of pure and salt-water [1]. Later, in 1855 Fick studied diffusion gradients between connected reservoirs [2]. From 1936 onward, Linderstrøm-Lang investigated the use of density gradient tubes for measurements of the density of macroscopic droplets and particles [2, 3]. Oster et al. gave an overview of different gradient preparation techniques [2]. When two miscible liquids of different density are brought in contact, diffusion leads to gradients. Density gradients can also be formed between liquids of different densities when mixed at different flow rates. Furthermore, gradients form on their own due to a thermodynamic distribution of suspension particles or macromolecules. Under high centrifugal pressure, even pure liquids form density gradients. However, due to the low compressibility, such gradients are small. This can be overcome with solutions that form gradients matching the density distribution of particles being studied. The self-forming gradient of a density medium was particularly introduced by Meselson, Vinograd and others [2]. Meselson et al. reported in 1957 that the concentration gradient of a solute of low molecular weight and compression of the solvent results in a continuous increasing density along the direction of centrifugal force, and studied band shapes [4]. In 1961, Hearst and Vinograd gave theoretical insights in the equilibrium in a density gradient [5]. Density gradient centrifugation is an efficient method for the separation of particles by density or size. If the centrifugation is continued until particles reach their equilibrium positions, the separation depends only on the particle density. On the other hand, if it is stopped prematurely, the separation occurs according to the sedimentation rates which depend on size. Large particles sediment faster than small ones. This method is referred to rate zonal separation [3, 6]. The distribution of particles in a density gradient might not always be true to the density of individual particles. Back in 1950, Brakke et al. stated that aggregation leads to a non-ideal sedimentation [3]. Price et al. reported that aggregates cause spurious distributions and anomalously high sedimentation rates [6].

Mateyko et al. assessed the usability of various density media for cell studies in 1963. They concluded, that a suspension of silica nanoparticles was the most suited available option [7]. Pertoft and Laurent introduced improvements in the following years like the development of modified colloidal silica and finally *Percoll* in 1978, a commercial density medium consisting of a suspension of coated silica particles, which had an improved non-toxicity to cells and low surface charge [8, 9]. Nowadays, Percoll is a standard medium for the density separation of erythrocytes,

leukocytes, liver cells, leydig cells, bone marrow cells, macrophages and many more cell types, subcellular particles including plasma membranes and cell organelles, as well as microorganisms like bacteria, viruses, parasites and algae [10].

As the main constituent of human blood, erythrocytes, also known as red blood cells (RBCs), were the subject of many studies in recent years. The flow properties of blood are mostly determined by red blood cells [11]. Their high deformability optimizes flow, enables passage through tiniest capillaries and is vital for nutrient transport and gas exchange [11–14]. The elastic properties are a result of the membrane structure [14]. Besides, the membrane owns a variety of ion channels, essential for nutrient and gas exchange [12, 15–19], some of them are linked to deformation by mechanical sensation [20]. It is known, that the density of red blood cells increases with their age [21, 22] during the life time of 120 days [16]. Therefore, centrifugation of erythrocytes in a density gradient allows a sorting by age. In 1980, Vettore et al. described a rapid method for the separation of RBCs in age-dependent fractions [23]. This led to a variety of studies on the relation of morphological parameters to cell age. The deformability of red blood cells declines during the aging process [24]. Lutz et al. found the deformability to be a reliable indicator for cell age [25]. The membrane protein 4.1 gives a reliable measure for cell age. While the total amount stays constant during the life time of a cell, the ratio between its forms 4.1a and 4.1b increases during ages as a conversion process takes place. Measurements of the protein ratio can be used to determine the exact cell age independent of other physiochemical parameters such as cell density [16, 17, 26].

The distribution of red blood cells after centrifugation in a self-forming Percoll gradient is surprisingly not homogeneous but characterized by a heterogeneous structure of discrete bands [23, 25, 27–32]. Bogdanova et al. suggested, that fractionation is linked to the activation of mechano-sensitive ion-channels and a resulting uptake of Ca^{2+} and loss of K^{+} [31]. Lutz et al. observed a redistribution of cells extracted from the gradient and concluded that a uniform density of cells from a particular fraction in the gradient is not guaranteed. Additionally, they suspected a contamination of dense cells in light fractions that reflected in the 4.1a to 4.1b measurements, and considered aggregation as a possible reason [25].

Recently, the quantification of band patterns by image processing was investigated and the applicability in diagnostics discussed. Sadafi et. al studied severity predictions of sickle cell anemia using graph convolutional networks [32]. While predictions based only of images of distributions in Percoll are not sufficient for a classification yet, a combination with complementary clinical data can improve accuracy.

The aim of our investigations was to study the dependency of the band structure on different physical and biochemical conditions. Furthermore we want to discuss a potential underlying mechanism, the aggregation of red blood cells.

2 Red Blood Cells and Percoll

The density distribution of a cell population can be resolved in a Percoll density gradient. The suspension of nanoparticles in a Percoll medium distributes during centrifugation in such a way that the resulting density of the suspension, i.e. particle concentration, increases along the centrifugation tube. Red blood cells sedimenting in this gradient distribute according to their density. However this distribution shows inhomogeneities which are related to morphological conditions and aggregation of erythrocytes. Those conditions depend on the activity of membrane channels, ion concentrations of the suspension, and membrane elasticity. The cell density is linked to cell age. Vice versa, measures of cell age are density markers.

2.1 Erythrocytes

Almost half of the volume of human blood is dedicated to cells. Moreover, nearly all cells suspended in blood are erythrocytes, also called red blood cells (RBCs) [13]. As the major constituent of mammalian blood, RBCs determine the majority of blood flow properties [11]. While plasma alone behaves like a Newtonian fluid, whole blood does not. One microliter of human blood contains five million erythrocytes, around 300 000 of platelets and 5000 to 8000 white cells, also called leukocytes [13]. White cells play an important role in the cell-mediated immune responses and antibody production [33]. In case of an injury blood will clot expressing serum into the blood plasma, and platelets are responsible for clot formation. Serum has a similar composition to plasma but misses fibrinogen [13]. The RBC cytosol contains hemoglobin molecules essential for gas transport in circulation. Red cells are also essential for the exchange of water and solutes when they are pressed against the endothelial wall of capillary blood vessels [13, 14]. The convey of oxygen from lungs to tissues and CO_2 in the opposite direction is mediated by hemoglobin and an anion exchange carrier in the RBC membrane. Of all CO_2 produced in the tissue, 85 % is carried in blood [12].

RBC Dynamics

Under uniform external pressure, red blood cells of all mammals possess the shape of a biconcave disk. This discocyte shape of human erythrocytes is approximately 7.5 to 8.7 μm in diameter and 1.7 to 2.2 μm in thickness. The membrane consists of a phospholipid bilayer with an underlying two-dimensional network of spectrin molecules and the enclosed volume averages to 94 fl at 300 mosmol/kg among humans.

Red blood cells' discocyte shape as well as elastic and biorheological properties are results of this structure. The bilayer mostly contributes to bending resistance while the spectrin network or cytoskeleton is largely responsible for shear elastic properties. Spectrin network and lipid bilayer are connected through integral and peripheral proteins. Those connections are referred to as vertical interactions [14]. In capillary flow, RBCs are stressed and deformed [13]. They show a variety of shapes including stationary and non-stationary configurations. Properties of RBC suspensions are determined by single particle behavior [11].

Aggregation

Three major classes of RBC aggregation are rouleaux formation, see Fig. 2.1, active adhesion in a blood clot, or pathological cases like malaria or sickle cell disease. The configuration of rouleaux aggregates looks similar to a stack of coins. Rouleaux formations are known to be caused by the presence of macromolecules like fibrinogen in blood plasma or upon suspension of isolated cells in solutions of dextran. The extent of aggregation depends on the molecular weight, e.g. the radius of gyration of dextran [34]. Neu et al. studied the dependency of RBC aggregation on the molecular mass and concentration of dextran [35]. Using dextran fractions between 70 kDa and 28 MDa, they discovered a bell-shaped behavior. The maximum extent of aggregation was located in the order of 1 MDa at the highest concentration of 0.9 g/dL. While the underlying adhesion mechanism is not fully understood, experimental and theoretical research indicates that rouleaux formation is mediated by depletion [34, 35]. Forces involved in the creation process of rouleaux are relatively weak, as aggregates can be broken up into smaller fractions or single cells by application of a sufficient but small shear force. This mechanism plays an important role in the shear thinning behavior of blood [34]. Also, aggregation is affected by intrinsic cell properties like membrane elasticity which contributes to the resistance of RBCs to aggregate [34, 36]. Measurements by Wagner et al. [34] showed a maximum interaction force magnitude of 170 pN in dextran of 150 kDa at 4 g/dl.

Fig. 2.1: Snapshot of rouleaux (a), schematic illustration of macromolecular bridging (b) and illustration of the depletion phenomenon (c) taken from [34]. Macromolecules are green, Colloid particles of diameter d_1 orange. White rings of diameter d_2 mark the exclusion volume of the colloid particles and dark blue areas the overlap volume. Due to the overlap, there is more volume available for macromolecules in the total volume in light blue. This leads to an entropic force.

Ion Channels

The physiological function of red blood cells is strongly dependent on the permeability properties of the membrane [18]. The cell membrane contains many ion channels which appear inactive in the resting cell. While the membrane is relatively impermeable to small cations, it is permeable to small anions. In equilibrium, chloride ions are distributed across the membrane while K^+ , Na^+ and Ca^{2+} are not. The equilibrium membrane potential in the resting cell is therefore determined by chloride [12, 18]. The unequal distribution of ions between the RBC and the plasma is maintained through the supply of glycolysis and ATP-fueled ion pumps [18, 19]. The membrane contains millions of a Cl^-/HCO_3^- exchangers like capnophorin, also referred to as band 3. This mechanism is highly efficient and important for the attainment of electroneutrality and the CO_2 carriage in blood [15, 18]. Ca-ATPase responds to Ca^{2+} by catalyzing hydrolysis of ATP and Na,K-ATPase exchanges three sodium ions by an influx of two potassium ions hydrolyzing ATP [15]. Each

membrane carries between one and two hundred of the Ca^{2+} activated K^+ channels referred to as Gárdos or IK_1 . A potassium outflux is initiated when the intracellular concentration of Ca^{2+} increases above a threshold. This leads to a hyperpolarization of the membrane since the potential is shifted from chloride to potassium and a consequential dehydration [12]. Mechanosensitive Piezo channels include Piezo1 and Piezo2. Their functions cover osmotic homeostasis, visceral and somatic mechanosensation, proprioception, blood flow sensing and epithelial homeostasis [20]. Piezo1 opens upon direct physical deformations of the lipid bilayer and mediates the exchange of both monovalent and divalent cations [15, 20]. A scheme of the energy providing process of glycolysis is depicted in figure Fig. 2.2.

Fig. 2.2: Illustration of the stimulation of glycolysis from Kuchel et al. [15]. GLUT1 is a glucose transporter delivering to the cytoplasm. Monocarboxylate transporter (MCT) mediates the facilitated diffusions of lactate across the membrane. For other mechanisms see text.

Tonicity

The osmolality of blood plasma in a healthy human is around 300 mosmol/kg [37]. Osmolality and osmolarity are measures of the osmotic pressure of a given solution. They quantify the concentration of ions that contribute to an osmotic pressure per volume or mass of solvent, respectively. Tonicity refers to the molality of specific solvents that cause a difference in osmotic pressure through a permeable membrane [38]. Concentrations falling below 300 mosmol/kg are referred to as hypoosmolar, while exceeding concentrations are called hyperosmolar, following the physiological conditions. Usually, those cases are also referred to as hypotonic and hypertonic. It should be noted, that those prefixes state comparisons to the isoosmolar condition, while effects on the cell morphology depend on specific ionic strengths. The Plasma osmolality is primarily determined by the sodium concentration [39]. A hypoosmotic environment induces morphological changes in erythrocytes that can lead to hemolysis [40], the opening of the cell membrane and resulting loss of hemoglobin. Those changes are associated with a decrease in RBC diameter and increase in volume at constant surface area [41, 42]. The mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) is proportional to the osmolality while the mean corpuscular volume (MCV) is inversely proportional [39, 42]. Reinhart et al. [39] investigated the role of osmolality of the suspension medium on RBC deformability and suspension viscosity. The osmolality was adjusted by altering the concentration of NaCl in the buffer solution. While hypoosmolality induced a spherical swelling, hyperosmolality dehydrated cells, which obtained a flattened discocyte shape, see figure Fig. 2.3. Moreover, the RBC deformability as measured by osmotic gradient ektacytometry showed a maximum at 290 mosmol/kg and was decreased in both hypo- or hyperosmotic environments. Besides the reduced deformability of spherical cells, hypotonically swollen RBCs have been shown to aggregate less [42].

Fig. 2.3: Scanning electron micrographs of RBCs in hypotonic, 189 mosmol/kg (a), and hypertonic, 431 mosmol/kg (b), solution by Reinhart et al. [39]. The difference in diameter might be exaggerated due to isotonic fixation in glutaraldehyde.

Morphological changes depend on concentrations of specific ions. A probable underlying mechanism is the opening of volume sensitive channels. Absorbance measurements by Nepal et al. showed, that among tested potassium salts KCl caused the second highest amount of lysis, and the highest among tested chloride salts [40]. Singh et al. recorded the amount of hemolysis by means of absorbance for different osmotic strengths. While lysis in NaCl or sucrose occurred for osmolalities below 150 mosmol/kg, red cells suspended in KCl lysed at 170 mosmol/kg and in CaCl_2 at 250 mosmol/kg [43]. Accordingly, the RBC density in a KCl buffer is lower compared to NaCl [44] at equal osmotic strengths.

Cell Aging

The life span of human erythrocytes in circulation is around 120 days [16]. Cohen et al. collected red blood cells, labeled and injected them back into the blood stream of the subject [45]. The amount of remaining cells was monitored over three months, see Fig. 2.4. Protein 4.1 is a component of the membrane skeleton that makes up around 5% of the total protein content of the membrane, which is 52%. There are two major forms in human, protein 4.1a with a mass of 80 kDa and 4.1b with 78 kDa [16]. The ratio of 4.1a and 4.1b depends on the RBC life span [46]. While the total amount of protein 4.1 remains constant, the ratio of 4.1a to 4.1b increases throughout the life of a red blood cell [16, 26]. This increase can be explained by the conversion from 4.1a to 4.1b. Protein 4.1 is synthesized as 4.1b which is therefore most dominant in immature erythroid cells. Thus, the 4.1a to 4.1b protein ratio can be used to determine the exact age independent of cell density [16, 17]. After density separation on a discontinuous stractan gradient, the MCV and MCHC correlate with the 4.1a/4.1b ratio [21]. Accordingly, during aging, the cell density increases [21, 22].

Fig. 2.4: Measurements by Cohen et al. [45]. Red blood cells were collected from diabetes mellitus patients (DM) and from a general population with hematologically normal blood (NDM). The curves only show the control measurements. The amount of labeled cells vanishes around 120 d. Curves are relatively linear due to a homogeneous starting age distribution and roughly constant death rate.

2.2 Percoll Density Medium

Mateyko and Kopac studied a plethora of suspensions for isopycnic cushioning in cellular studies back in 1963 [7]. They discussed numerous advantages of such a medium like the division of highly heterogeneous populations in discrete layers, the sorting applications of the variety of tumor cells, and the cell protection employed by the cushioning in high accelerations. An isopycnic cushion is a medium, that will support cells during centrifugation maintaining a viable state. In their work, several requirements for a suitable suspension medium were established. Its density must approximate the cell density. Moreover, the medium must be compatible with the cells' usual milieu, should be dispersible or soluble in aqueous solutions, provide a stable pH at cellular ranges, remain dispersed at extremes of temperatures, possess a low viscosity, and have an initial high specific gravity, i.e. a high molecular or particle weight. Furthermore, the constituents should not penetrate cell membranes, be isotonic in the isopycnic range, and overall innocuous to cells. Many candidates for a cushioning medium showed pitfalls. Bovine or human serum albumin (BSA, HSA) only provide useful densities in large concentrations rendering the medium expensive and impractical. Globulin requires dialysis and, like gelatine, has a low specific weight. Polyvinyl alcohol introduces cell shrinkage, is too viscous, and not dense enough. Polyglucose has a good morphological maintenance but its density is too low. Heterocyclic polymers like polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) are too viscous or cause cell distortion. *Colloidal silica however turned out to be an effective medium for isopycnic cushioning.* A dispersion of spherical particles of amorphous silica, SiO₂, 30% (w/w) in deionized water, with a diameter of 15 to 20 nm was stable also at low pH and matched the conditions best. Dissymmetric particles could be removed by centrifugation such that the resulting viscosity was low due to the spherical shape of the remaining particles. Commercially, colloidal silica was available as *Ludox* at 15 to 30% (m/m), a pH between 8.5 and 9.8 due to alkali stabilization, and diameters of 7 to 15 micron.

Silica sols were mixed with various polymers including dextran, polyethylene glycol and PVP. These polymers were found to protect cells and other biological materials from interaction with silica particles. Nontoxic, highly soluble modified colloidal silica (MCS) of low charge and viscosity were developed [8]. In 1978, Pertoft et al. presented the advantages of colloidal silica particles firmly coated with a layer of polyvinylpyrrolidone [9]. This medium was called *Percoll*.

Nowadays, commercially available Percoll comes with a mean dry particle diameter of 21 to 22 nm with a variation between 15 and 30 nm as measured from microscopic examinations [10, 47]. The molecular weight is 6 MDa. At low ionic strength, hydrated particles show a PVP network on the surface acting as a polyelectrolyte. At higher ionic strengths of around 300 mosmol/kg, the average hydrodynamic diameter is 30 nm [47].

While many protocols use discontinuous Percoll gradients, the sedimentation distribution of nanoparticles causes the development of a continuous density gradient, if the centrifugal force is high enough [9,47]. Discontinuous gradients are prepared by carefully layering liquids of different density. Consequently it consists of discrete phases each of homogeneous density apart from diffusion [6]. *GE Healthcare Bio-Sciences* did measurements of the Percoll density as a function of height in the centrifugation tube, see Fig. 2.5. They investigated shapes of self-formed gradients for various centrifugation durations and different concentrations of stock medium at multiple centrifugal accelerations [10]. Laurent et al. studied the dependency of the gradient shape on the rotor angle [48]. Pertoft et al. did electron microscopy imaging of the modified colloidal silica contained in Percoll [8,47].

Results from *GE Healthcare*, Laurent et al. and Pertoft et al. are shown in figure Fig. 2.5. In an angle-head rotor, the density gradient is sigmoidal and becomes steeper with increasing centrifugation duration. The density function is closer to a constant homogeneous starting density for short durations and closer to a linear gradient as time progresses. When the concentration of the Percoll stock suspension is decreased, the gradient shows a shift of its central density towards the respective starting density, and simultaneously a slight stretch towards the bottom of the tube. However, the overall shape is preserved. As the centrifugal force is increased, the gradient becomes steeper compared to a lower force. The effect of acceleration on the steepness of the density function is much larger than the effect of centrifugation duration. It is steepest for the highest concentration of Percoll. In a fixed angle rotor with a smaller angle between the tube axis and the lot, the gradient is more linear.

Fig. 2.5: The curves in (a) show gradient measurements using colored beads in an angle-head rotor of the same medium at $20,000 \times g$ for different centrifugation duration. The source images of the bead distributions are shown in (d). Graphs in (b) show gradient measurements for different concentrations of stock isotonic Percoll. The rotor angle was 23° and running conditions were $30,000 \times g$ for 15 min. Measurements in equal conditions but at $60,000 \times g$ were performed (c). Image (e) shows electron microscopy of Percoll particles. Different angles were explored for equivalent conditions of $30,000 \times g$ for 14 min in (f). All figures were (re-)produced by *GE Healthcare* [10].

3 Experimental Investigations

A variety of experiments have been conducted to study the influence of physical and biochemical conditions on the sedimentation distribution of red blood cells in a Percoll density gradient. Due to the complexity and diversity of the investigations, this chapter is subdivided in many sections.

3.1 Band Structure in Standard Conditions

Examples of our distribution after centrifugation are provided in Fig. 3.1. It shows samples, that were centrifuged under the same conditions in the same rotor. For the same initial distribution, the resulting pattern is consistent up to small variations.

The distribution of Red Blood Cells in a Percoll gradient of matching density is known to show a structure of discrete bands [23, 25, 27–32]. After centrifugation, this pattern is alike in two tubes if the conditions, like the blood sample, the medium density and buffer composition as well as the centrifugation conditions are equal. In that sense, the band structure is deterministic. The observed consistency between patterns of equal origin indicates, that the resulting distribution depends on the initial conditions and the time dependent centrifugation process, only. Hence, it is reproducible to the degree of controlling these conditions. Variations in the pattern only occur due to differences in those.

Examples for influential factors are the buffer and Percoll medium compositions controlled by volumetric measurements, the temperature in the centrifuge regulated by a heat pump, the osmolality measured or preadjusted in a stock or commercial stock solution, and the origin and condition of the blood sample. Volumes are usually measured using manual pipettes like the *Eppendorf Research plus* which have errors up to 1 % or more [49]. Volumetric measurements also depend on the ambient temperature in the lab, since fluid densities change. The temperature regulation during centrifugation depends on the ambient lab temperature. Also, an increased rotor imbalance comes with a higher amount of friction. These effects possibly influence the temperature curve during centrifugation. Furthermore, the osmolality depends on the medium composition. If the medium is made on site, osmolality underlies fluctuations as it depends on volume measurements. During storage as a stock solution, CO₂ can be absorbed and H₂O evaporated, both causing an increase in osmolality and changes in the pH. Blood samples from different donors usually show different cell densities and dynamics resulting in differences

Fig. 3.1: Distribution after centrifugation at equal conditions, namely $20\,000 \times g$ at 34°C for 30 min. The first three tubes from the left contain aliquotes of blood sample A and show results from the day of blood collection. The fourth shows a centrifugation of A on the following day under equal conditions. In contrast, the initial condition was a mixed homogeneous distribution in the fifth tube that contains a new blood sample, B. The last tube shows B on the same day with topped initial condition.

in the distribution. If experiments on the same sample are conducted successively, the blood composition and cell characteristics will change in between as metabolic processes continue [50, 51]. The reproducibility for equal blood samples was also pointed out by Vettore et al. [23].

Besides from these influences, we observe deterministic results that do not significantly depend on intrinsic statistical processes. Variations occur due to differences in initial or external conditions.

3.2 Initial Distribution

During high speed centrifugation of red blood cells in a Percoll medium, there are two dynamic processes running simultaneously. Each cell sediments towards an equilibrium position where the net force on it is zero. At the same time, the silica nanoparticles sediment and distribute to form a density gradient. In this subsection, we distinguish different spatial initial RBC distributions along the vertical axis of the centrifugation tube.

Experimental Methods

Percoll medium was made by diluting commercial stock suspension to 90 % with a ten times concentrated buffer. The resulting medium was therefore isotonic and had a pH of 7.4. If a pH adjustment was necessary, HCl or NaOH were used. Percoll medium was filled in a centrifugation tube. Afterwards, either full blood or a sample of washed red cells in an equivalent hematocrit and the same buffer like in the medium was added. The sample to medium ratio was around 7 % to 8 % (v/v). For details on the preparation refer to section 6.2 in the appendix.

The two initial distributions that are easiest to achieve experimentally are the *topped* and the *mixed* initial condition. In the topped case, the blood sample of a hematocrit of around 50 % is carefully released on top of the interface of the Percoll medium to obtain a top phase. On the other hand, a homogeneous distribution in the total volume is referred to as the mixed condition and is usually achieved by a gentle rotation of the tube, after the blood sample has been added.

Images in Fig. 3.2 show a comparison of the initial conditions and the resulting distributions after centrifugation. The blood sample that was homogeneously distributed was washed to isolate RBCs from other blood constituents. The washing has no significant effect on the distribution pattern as discussed in section 3.8. Compared to the topped initial condition, the mixed condition results in a less pronounced band pattern.

Discussion

For both initial distributions, a band formation was observed. The differences in the distribution patterns originate in the differences in the initial cell distribution. This indicates that the dynamics during the sedimentation have influence on the result. If the result represented an equilibrium configuration that only depends on intrinsic single cell characteristics like the individual density, it would be independent of the initial distribution. Furthermore, these observations show that band formation also occurs when cells are significantly more separated initially, i.e. if the volume concentration is lower.

Fig. 3.2: Initial RBC distributions and resulting patterns after centrifugation at 34°C and $20000 \times g$ for 30 min in Chur buffered Percoll medium. From left to right, topped condition before and after, mixed condition after and before centrifugation. The mixed sample was washed and hence does not contain plasma. The mixed sample shows a band structure that is less pronounced compared to the topped condition. Samples are exemplary and stem from different runs. The image to the right shows the mixed sample and a control sample in a light box for increased visibility.

3.3 Time Dependency and Acceleration

The shape of a self-formed Percoll gradient shows a time dependent development [10,47]. Also, it depends on the centrifugal force as measurements by *GE Healthcare* show, see Fig. 2.5. Experiments were carried out to monitor the red blood cell distribution during gradient formation and to study variations after sedimentation through different accelerations.

Experimental Methods

A sample of venous blood was collected from a healthy donor. After making a standard *Chur* buffered Percoll medium, 1 ml was placed on top of 12.5 ml medium in a 15 ml tube. With the acceleration time set to 5 min it was centrifuged for 10 min at $20000 \times g$, decelerated, and a picture was taken. The process was repeated five times.

Two equal samples were prepared in the same way as before but with PBS as a buffer. One sample was centrifuged at $20\,000 \times g$ for 30 min and the other at $50\,000 \times g$ for 15 min.

Discussion

The resulting images show the evolution of the distribution in the self-forming Percoll gradient, see Fig. 3.3. The width of the distribution first increases and reaches a maximum after around 20 min. Then, the distribution narrows and the number of layers decreases as they come closer indicating a merging process. During the first few minutes, some cells move down towards the bottom of the tube as the blood sample was topped. Afterwards, the direction reverses. On the other hand, some cells stay at the top and only show a downward movement. The plasma phase becomes broader and loses opacity as the Percoll gradient forms and an increasing portion of the buffer towards the top becomes depleted of nanoparticles. Initially, the gradient is small causing cells with a density greater than the initial medium density to accelerate down and lighter cells up, respectively. As the sigmoidal shape develops, a focusing takes place due to the fact, that the gradient becomes steeper near bottom and top, and the shallow saddle spans over all cell densities.

Distributions after two different accelerations and adapted duration are shown in Fig. 3.4. The spread is narrower in case of a higher acceleration and the number of layers is lower. Cells that are spread across three to four bands in the first sample, appear to be incorporated in two thicker bands. Also, the plasma phase is larger for a stronger acceleration. As Fig. 2.5 shows, a higher centrifugal force renders the density function steeper overall which leads to a focusing of the cell distribution. The sample with lower acceleration was centrifuged for a longer time. A longer duration is associated with a steeper gradient, but the influence of acceleration is much larger as the measurements with density markers suggest.

Fig. 3.3: Time evolution of the distribution of red blood cells in a self-forming Percoll gradient. Each image shows the previous state after centrifugation for an additional 10 min. The times for acceleration of 5 min as well as deceleration are not included. The buffer was 350 mosmol/kg *Chur* and centrifugation conditions were $20\,000 \times g$ at 34°C . From the initial topped condition some cells moved towards the tube bottom before reversing direction, while others remained on top showing a downward motion. The distribution undergoes a focusing over time with a decrease in width and number of layers. Samples were repeatedly disturbed due to the braking process and manual handling. Therefore, the structure became asymmetrical and less pronounced. The plasma phase on top of the sample increases in height and loses opacity.

Fig. 3.4: Resulting distributions for 1 ml of blood that was layered on top of 12.5 ml of the same *Chur* buffered Percoll medium each. The centrifugation conditions were $20\,000 \times g$ for 30 min in the left image, and $50\,000 \times g$ for 15 min in the right one. The plasma phase is slightly larger in case of a higher centrifugal force.

3.4 Rotor Geometry

Throughout this study, various centrifuges equipped with individual rotors were used. Rotors included angle-head and swing out models and required different tube dimensions.

Experimental Methods

Four different centrifuges with various rotors were used. Venous blood from healthy donors was collected. In case of washing for RBC isolation, an isotonic buffer was used and the hematocrit restored to around 50%. Isotonic Percoll media of 81% concentration were prepared using concentrates of buffers. Blood samples were added to a volumetric proportion of 7 to 10%. For more detail on the preparation refer to the appended section 6.2.

Discussion

The configurations are listed in Tab. 3.1. Examples for sedimentation distributions are shown in figure Fig. 3.5 for each centrifuge setup. At lower angle (I) and (II) with 26° and 28° respectively, the distributions are narrower compared to the other configurations of equal tube geometry, (III) or (IV). From measurements of the angle dependent gradient shape, see section 2.2 Fig. 2.5, one knows that the density function adopts a more pronounced sigmoidal shape. That means, there is a saddle near the center and steep wings towards the tube bottom and top. The steeper gradient induces a focusing and the shallow central region a spread. This effect is further explored in section 3.5. As the sigmoidal shape develops with larger angles, distributions show an increased width in the 34° and 90° rotors (III) and (IV) due to the low gradient magnitude.

In all cases, the sedimentation distribution showed a band structure. *Therefore it can be concluded that a fixed angle rotor and the resulting incline as well as the associated constraining forces are not necessary prerequisites for the formation of bands.* In a swing out rotor, the centrifugal force is directed parallel to the tube axis at all times. Angular accelerations were kept low in those experiments.

Group	Centrifuge	Rotor	Angle	Label
Wagner	<i>Hermle Z36 HK</i>	<i>221.22</i>	26° - fixed	I
Bogdanova	<i>Sorvall Lynx 4000</i>	<i>A22-24x16</i>	28° - fixed	II
Minetti	<i>Sorvall RC 5B Plus</i>	<i>SS-34</i>	34° - fixed	III
Philippa	<i>Beckman Coulter Optima XPN-80</i>	<i>SW 32 Ti</i>	90° - swing out	IV

Tab. 3.1: Centrifuges and Rotors used in this study. Each configuration is labeled for reference. The *SW 32 Ti* is a swing out rotor.

Fig. 3.5: Isotonic sedimentation distributions after centrifugation in the configurations listed and labeled in Tab. 3.1. The medium concentration was 81 % in all cases. (I) shows 0.6 ml washed blood with restored hematocrit mixed in 8 ml Percoll in a 10 ml tube of 1.6 cm diameter. Running conditions were $20\,000 \times g$ for 20 min at 25 °C. On top of 12.5 ml Percoll, 1 ml full blood was layered in a 15 ml tube of 1.8 cm diameter in configuration (II). Centrifugation was carried out at 34 °C and $20\,000 \times g$ for 30 min. In (III), 1 ml full blood was layered on top of 13 ml Percoll in a 15 ml tube and centrifuged under equal conditions to (I). Setup (IV) uses a swing out rotor, conditions were equal to (I) with the exception of a full blood sample.

3.5 Cell-Free Zone

In some cases, the distribution of erythrocytes showed a cell-free zone, and close to the tube center. This effect was most frequently observed in a 26° angle head rotor using 10 ml tubes and a standard 81 % Percoll medium with an amount of 7% whole blood. An example is depicted on the left hand side of Fig. 3.6. The self-formed Percoll density gradient is flat around its center. Given the density as a function of position $\rho(x)$ as well as the distribution of RBC densities in terms of a probability density $p_{\text{cell}}(\rho)$ the expected equilibrium distribution of cells along the tube height $g(x)$ can be computed following

$$p_{\text{cell}}(\rho) d\rho = g(x) dx \Rightarrow g(x) = p_{\text{cell}}(\rho) \frac{d\rho}{dx}. \quad (3.1)$$

The cell density was assumed to follow a gaussian distribution with a mean density of 1.0933 g/ml and a standard deviation of 4 mg/ml in accordance with [52, 53]. In order to obtain a gradient function, a polynomial of degree nine was fitted to experimental data from *GE Healthcare* from a 23° angle head rotor in a similar concentration of 80 % Percoll [10]. The derivative of the polynomial was computed analytically. Additionally, the gradient was flattened numerically to investigate the effect on the final distribution. The adjusted gradient was integrated and the average density matched to the original fit function. Density functions and deduced probability densities are shown in Fig. 3.6 to the right. While the interpolated experimental data only causes an insignificant dip close to the center of the RBC distribution, the adjusted function leads to a cell-free zone. The width of this cell-free region increases with a decrease in the gradient magnitude. In the extreme case of a constant density, cells would be completely separated building a top phase with $\rho_{\text{cell}} < \rho_{\text{medium}}$ and a bottom phase for $\rho_{\text{cell}} > \rho_{\text{medium}}$.

Discussion

No available experimental data could explain a cell-free zone of the extent that was observed in experiments. However, the cell-free zone could potentially be caused by a shallow saddle of the density function. Measurements of the gradient usually involve marker beads [10, 47] or the division of the tube volume into layers. These layers are extracted and the density of each layer is measured. For that purpose, the volume per layer must be sufficient for an accurate result. This however limits the resolution due to an averaging. Unfortunately, there exists no sufficiently resolved measurement of the gradient yet for the specific results of the utilized rotor and tubes.

Fig. 3.6: Example of a cell-free zone between 3.7 and 3.9 cm. Centrifugation conditions were 25°C and $20\,000 \times g$ for 20 min in an isotonic PBS buffered 81 % medium without BSA. The sample volume was 8.6 ml with a blood share of 7 % (v/v). The rotor angle was 26° to the lot. On the right, the density as a function of position is plotted. The curve from a measurement by *GE-Healthcare* [10] (blue) was adjusted to be flatter around its center (red). From both curves the expected pdf of the distribution of RBCs was computed using Eqn. (3.1). The adjusted density curve, red and dashed, can explain the cell free zone.

3.6 Experiments with Layer Isolation

During high speed centrifugation of a Percoll suspension, a density gradient is formed [47]. The density distribution of RBCs is resolved by sedimentation in this gradient. In addition, separated bands of cells form a substructure of the enveloping distribution [27–32]. In our experiments, cells from several of these bands were collected. Each of the set of cells originating from the same band was washed, resuspended and centrifuged in Percoll a second time.

Experimental Methods

A volume of 0.8 ml full blood of a healthy donor was layered on top of 7.8 ml of a 80 % (v/v) Percoll medium in a 10 ml centrifugation tube. The sample was centrifuged at $20,000 \times g$ maximum relative acceleration for 20 min at 25°C in an angled rotor of 26° . The resulting distribution showed a band structure. Using a syringe pump and microfluidic tubing, several sets of cells from different bands were collected, washed 3 times in PBS using a 15 ml *Cellstar* tube and resuspended to restore a hematocrit of around 50%. The setup is illustrated in Fig. 3.7. This method allows for a clean extraction of almost entire bands without introducing relevant disturbances. In a first iteration, a band of lower density (L_1) and a band of higher density (H_1) were collected. Consequently, the remaining bands were more separated afterwards. A low density (L_2) a medium density (M_2) and a high density (H_2) band were extracted in a second iteration, see Fig. 3.8. The resuspended samples were centrifuged a second time in 7.8 ml of a 80 % (v/v) Percoll medium under equal conditions. Two samples L_1 and H_1 were extracted, washed and mixed. The hematocrit was restored and the combined set of cells centrifuged a third time.

Fig. 3.7: Extraction of cells from a single band. Micro medical tubing, 0.9 mm i.d. and 1.3 mm o.d., was carefully inserted in the centrifugation tube and guided through the band structure until the end reaches the desired band. A syringe pump provided a constant volumetric flow rate of approximately $40 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. The tube position was slowly adjusted manually.

Fig. 3.8: Band structure during removal of several bands. The image on the far left shows the pattern after centrifugation and before cell extraction. Each of the following photographs of the same tube shows the state on its left after removing cells from the marked band. The bands are labeled according to their density.

Fig. 3.9: The extracted cells from the bands of the full structure, see Fig. 3.8, were resuspended and centrifuged a second time in the same Percoll medium. On the left, samples from the first iteration, samples from the second iteration on the right. The cells of L_1 and H_1 were extracted, mixed and centrifuged a third time. All experiments show an additional sub-band structures. The low density layer L_1 was absorbed in the height density layer H_1 after mixing, see $L_1 + H_1$. Since the volumes of the samples $L_1 + H_1$ and L_2 were higher, the medium densities were lower.

Discussion

The distributions of the extracted set of cells after centrifugation are depicted in Fig. 3.9. The amount of PBS in the suspension changes the density of the Percoll medium. As a consequence, the resulting density gradients were shifted since the sample volumes varied. Apart from that, all distributions showed band structures. The distribution of each set of cells was broader than the band the set originated from.

When assuming a similar gradient in both the original and the resuspended samples, a broadening of the cell distribution can be explained by a previous agglomeration and rearrangement into a new configuration. For a supplementary experiment see appendix 6.4. Lutz et al. [25] also reported a redistribution after extraction from a Percoll gradient and suspected aggregation to be the reason.

Various biochemical conditions were established, tested and the resulting distribution patterns compared. Such conditions include the buffer constitution and osmolality, the activation and inhibition of calcium and potassium channels, the effect of trypsin and storage of red blood cells.

3.7 Phosphate and HEPES buffer

Two different buffers were used. PBS is a widely used phosphate buffer and Chur a rich HEPES-based buffer that is closer to blood plasma in its constitution.

Experimental Methods

Chur is a solution named after the capital of the Swiss canton of the Grisons. The richness in its ingredients renders the buffer plasma-like. It is thought to create an appropriate environment for Erythrocytes comparable to natural conditions. The buffer contains 140 mM NaCl, 4 mM KCl, 0.75 mM MgSO₄, 10 mM glucose, 0.015 mM ZnCl₂, 0.2 mM glycine, 0.2 mM glutamate, 0.1 mM arginine, 0.6 mM glutamine, 0.2 mM alanine and 20 mM HEPES imidazole following Makhro et al. [28]. Two Percoll suspensions with equal concentrations of 81 % of the commercial stock were prepared. The density was 1.113 g/ml, respectively. Also, two different conditions of centrifugation were studied for each buffer, namely 50 000 × *g* for 15 min and 20 000 × *g* for 30 min.

Discussion

The resulting structures are shown in Fig. 3.10. They are similar in terms of the number of bands, but PBS shows a shift towards the tube bottom in both cases. The most likely explanation is a difference in osmolality or pH. When stored in contact to air, the absorption of CO₂ leads to a decrease in pH and a shrinkage of cells [54]. An increase in osmolality is connected with an increase in density, see section 3.11.

Fig. 3.10: Comparison between sedimentation distributions in different buffer solutions. The Percoll concentration was 81 % (v/v) in both cases. Samples accelerated with 20 000 × *g* show a broader distribution. In a phosphate buffered environment, the structures are similar in the number of layers compared to the HEPES based Chur buffer condition. PBS introduces a shift towards the bottom compared to Chur.

3.8 Full versus Washed Blood

In order to investigate the effects of plasma constituents on the sedimentation distribution, the blood sample was washed prior to centrifugation to isolate the red blood cells.

Experimental Methods

A Percoll medium of 81 %, buffered with Chur was prepared. Venous blood was drawn from a healthy donor into a tube containing heparin. Two sample of 1 ml each were extracted. One sample was washed three times at $1700 \times g$ for 5 min in Chur. The liquid phase was removed and the total volume of the sample was restored to 1 ml. Both samples were centrifuged at 34°C and $20\,000 \times g$ for 20 min.

Discussion

The resulting distributions are presented in Fig. 3.11 . The banding patterns compare well. This indicates, that the band formation phenomenon depends mostly on the properties of red blood cells, and no other blood constituents are involved.

Fig. 3.11: Distribution after centrifugation of a full (left) and a washed (right) blood sample in the same run at $20\,000 \times g$ and 34°C for 30 min in isotonic conditions. The 81 % Percoll medium was buffered with Chur. The washed sample was adjusted to the same volume and hence contains the same amount of erythrocytes. As the images show, the band structures are equivalent to the eye. An effect of plasma was not observed.

3.9 Calcium and Potassium Channels

The influence of calcium and potassium flux was investigated using different drugs prior to centrifugation. RBC treatment was carried out by Asya Makhro, Zürich.

Experimental Methods

Yoda1 is a specific activator of mouse and human cation channel Piezo1, a mechanosensitive channel that mediates Ca^{2+} influx on mechanical activation [20]. Tram34 is an inhibitor of Ca^{2+} -dependent K^{+} channels [55]. NS309 is a Ca^{2+} -activated IK/SK potassium channel activator [56]. Each drug was dissolved in DMSO, which was also added to the control sample in the same concentration.

Discussion

The treatment with Tram34 shows the smallest effect as the resulting pattern matches the control. Cells exposed to NS309 form bands with a similar distribution compared to the control. However, a subset of cells appears denser. The largest effect has the Piezo1 activator Yoda1 as the resulting distribution is more homogenous, i.e. the band separation decreased.

Fig. 3.12: Blood samples have been drugged prior to centrifugation in equal conditions. DMSO was added as a solvent to all samples, including the control (CNT). All samples show signs of hemolysis. Tram34 compares well to the control, NS309 shows denser cells near the tube bottom. Cells treated with Yoda1 show a more homogeneous distribution and less band separation.

3.10 Surface Charges and Storage

Charges on the surface of the red blood cell membrane can influence interaction forces. Trypsin was used, which is known to increase aggregation [57].

Experimental Methods

To 15 ml of a solution of 0.05 % trypsin and 0.02 % EDTA in PBS thawed at 37°C 1 ml of full fresh blood from a healthy donor was added. The suspension was gently homogenized and incubated for 45 min on a roller at room temperature. Erythrocytes were washed by centrifugating three times at room temperature and $2000 \times g$ for 5 min. A control sample of the same volume was treated in the same way. After washing, a total volume of 1 ml per sample was restored by adding PBS, restoring the original hematocrit. A standard 81 % isotonic Percoll medium buffered with PBS and without BSA was prepared. Aliquotes of 0.6 ml were taken from each of the two samples and added to 8 ml of density medium. For a mixed initial condition, the samples were gently rotated until the cell distribution was homogenized. Both samples were centrifuged together at equal conditions at 25°C and $20\,000 \times g$ for 20 min.

After the images of the resulting distributions had been taken, both samples were washed and stored in PBS for 72 h on a roller at room temperature. Afterwards, the original volume of 600 μl was restored. A second centrifugation was carried out under the same conditions as the first.

Discussion

The resulting distributions are presented in Fig. 3.13. The band structure of cells treated with trypsin appears similar compared to the control sample. There is no significant effect of trypsin under the established experimental standard conditions. Furthermore, images to the right of Fig. 3.13 show the final distributions. In the case of cells that were stored, both samples show more homogeneous distributions with thinner bands that are higher in number. However, cells treated with trypsin show slightly more pronounced bands compared to the control.

During storage, erythrocytes lose their deformability and show an increased rigidity [58, 59]. The RBC shape changes from discocyte to spherocyte or spherocytocyte [50, 60]. During storage of citrated whole blood, the reaggregation declines strongly during one day and the ability to form rouleaux configurations is lost by 50 % during one week [61]. The deformability plays an important role in rouleaux formation [36]. Due to storage in PBS, the aggregation ability was potentially lost. Moreover, the enhanced agglomeration ability by trypsin could explain the more pronounced band formation in the treated sample after storage. The influence of agglomeration on band formation was further investigated in the following.

Fig. 3.13: Distributions after centrifugation at $20\,000 \times g$ and $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 min in 10 ml centrifugation tubes. The sample volume was $600\ \mu\text{l}$. In each picture, the tube to the right shows cells drugged with trypsin. There is no significant effect of trypsin, as the band structure is close to the control. Both sample were stored in PBS for 72 h. Afterwards, the hematocrit was restored and the centrifugation was repeated at equal conditions, see right picture. The resulting structures show more homogeneous distributions with higher numbers of thin bands. Here, trypsinized cells show more pronounced bands.

3.11 Osmolality

In the circulatory system in vivo, the plasma osmolality is around 300 mosmol/kg [37]. Accordingly, an osmolality below is considered hypotonic and above hypertonic. In a first experiment, the effect of media with different osmotic strengths was studied.

3.11.1 Hypo- and Hypertonic Conditions

In a first experiment, the osmolality of the buffer and Percoll medium was decreased or increased to obtain a hypotonic or a hypertonic environment, respectively. The effect on the sedimentation distribution was studied.

Experimental Methods

To 27 ml of Percoll in a 50 ml *Falcon* tube 3 ml of $7\times Chur$ and 3.3 ml of $0.7\times Chur$ were added. The dilution of $7\times Chur$ was prepared by mixing 3.5 ml $10\times Chur$ with 1.5 ml MilliQ, $0.7\times Chur$ equally starting with $1\times Chur$ containing 1‰ of BSA. Since the $1\times Chur$ had an osmolality of 350 mosmol/kg, the hypotonic medium was expected to turn out at 245 mosmol/kg and measured with 250 mosmol/kg. Hypertonic medium was prepared by adding 3.9 ml of $10\times Chur$ and 4.3 ml of $1\times Chur$ containing BSA. The resulting osmolality was 450 mosmol/kg. Since the starting concentration was $10\times Chur$, the density of the hypertonic medium was lower. All measurements of osmolality were performed using a freezing point osmometer.

Discussion

The distributions in a hypotonic and hypertonic environment are shown in Fig. 3.14. An increase in osmolality causes a gain in density while a decrease in osmolality causes a reduction. The global change in cell density introduces a shift in the distribution. In the sigmoidal Percoll gradient, this shift manifests in a narrowing of the distribution towards the top or bottom of the tube, respectively. On the other hand, regions that are closer to the tube ends in the control are now located around the center and therefore show a broader, more resolved spread.

In hypertonic solution, cells undergo a shrinkage forming echinocytes, while a hypotonic environment causes swelling and stomatocyte shapes [62]. If mass conservation is assumed, meaning there is only in- or out-flux of water, the change in volume is directly connected to a change in density. The highest density resolution is achieved, where the gradient is weak and centered around the average density. When the average density is changed, the majority of cells sediment to a position, where the gradient is steep. By adjusting the centrifugation conditions, the gradient shape can be manipulated [10, 47]. The comparison between conditions are depicted in Fig. 3.15. In the case of 450 mosmol/kg, lowering the centrifugal force causes the gradient magnitude to decrease. Hence, the distribution shows a broader spread.

Fig. 3.14: The Percoll medium was adjusted to obtain a hypertonic and a hypotonic environment. The images show the resulting distributions for 450 mosmol/kg and 250 mosmol/kg as well as a control sample of 350 mosmol/kg. A lower osmolality correlates with a decrease in density and vice versa.

Fig. 3.15: The centrifugation conditions were changed from 15 min at $50\,000 \times g$ to 15 min at $20\,000 \times g$ for the hypertonic and 30 min at $50\,000 \times g$ for the hypotonic sample. In case of 450 mosmol/kg, the alteration lead to an enhancement of the distribution resolution.

When increasing centrifugation time in the case of 250 mosmol/kg from 15 min to 30 min at equal centrifugal force, the gradient magnitude is increased which narrows down the distribution.

An adjustment of the centrifugation conditions can enhance the resolution, like in the case of the hypertonic sample. However it is not suitable to obtain a good representation of the full distribution as the time constant of gradient formation is smaller than the time constant of RBC sedimentation, see appendix 6.9.

3.11.2 Density Matching

As discussed in chapter 2.2, the Percoll gradient develops around the mean density of the initially homogenous suspension. In order to archive an optimal distribution of Red Cells across the tube length, the average density of the Percoll medium needs to be matched to the average cell density. The density of erythrocytes depends on the ionic concentration in the surrounding solution, see section 3.11.1.

Experimental Methods

For each individual buffer composition, a centrifugation series with various Percoll concentrations was prepared. The same volume of 100 μl blood sample was mixed homogenously into 1 ml of each of the Percoll media. Then, the tubes were centrifuged at $1400 \times g$ for 5 min. In order to avoid formation of a density gradient, a low relative centrifugal force was used. The sedimentation of RBCs is characterized by a much smaller time scale then the gradient development, refer to appendix 6.9. After centrifugation, the amount of cells on the bottom of the tube was compared to the amount of cells on top by eye. Assuming a symmetric density distribution of RBCs, the medium matches the average cell density best, when it separates the sample into two equal quantities.

Discussion

The samples for isotonic PBS are presented in Fig. 3.16. A concentration of 80.1 % of the commercial stock Percoll suspension was chosen as the best match out of the series. The corresponding medium density and therefore the approximate average cell density was 1.102 g/ml. For the density calculation, the densities of buffer and blood plasma were taken into account. The same matching procedure was used for hypotonic samples. In the case of 154 mosmol/kg, the best matching density was 1.068 g/ml at a concentration of 51.3 % Percoll. For supplementary information refer to section 6.1 in the appendix.

concentration	76.5	78.3	80.1	81.9	83.7	85.5
$\rho_{PC}[\text{g/ml}]$	1.1052	1.1076	1.1099	1.1123	1.1146	1.1170
$\rho_{PC+plasma}[\text{g/ml}]$	1.0975	1.0996	1.1018	1.1039	1.1060	1.1082

Fig. 3.16: Density matching for erythrocytes in an isotonic suspension in PBS. The osmolality was isotonic at 307 mosmol/kg. Tubes with Percoll media of different concentrations containing a homogenous mixture of equal blood samples were centrifuged at low speed. The best match was determined by eye, at $x = 6$ cm. It was assumed to be the tube with the most equal division of RBCs to top and bottom of the tube. In the case of isotonic PBS buffered Percoll medium, a concentration of 80.1% of the commercial stock, i.e. a density of 1.102 g/ml respectively, compares best to the average cell density. The influence of the blood plasma density on the resulting mixture was taken into account.

3.11.3 Strong Hypotonic Environment

In section 3.11.1 we discussed that changes in the buffer osmolality causes the distribution to shift vertically. The band structure was affected and changing the centrifugation conditions was unsatisfying in restoring a good resolution. In the following experiments the effect of a strongly hypotonic environment close to hemolysis was studied. For best comparability to control samples, a density matching procedure was used, see section 3.11.2.

Experimental Methods

PBS buffered Percoll media of different densities were prepared. To 45 ml of stock Percoll, 5 ml of 10×PBS was added for the isotonic and 4×PBS for the hypotonic medium, respectively. A few droplets of HCl were added to lower the pH to 7.4. In case of an undershoot, NaOH was used. The isotonic medium had an osmolality of 301 mosmol/kg, and the hypotonic 170 mosmol/kg, as measured with a *Knauer Osmometer Automatic* freezing point osmometer. The density was adjusted in 10 ml centrifugation tubes. For the isotonic sample, 7 ml isotonic Percoll medium and 0.777 ml of PBS were mixed, for the hypotonic, 4.56 ml hypotonic Percoll medium and 3.44 ml, respectively. Both samples were centrifuged at the same time at a relative centrifugal force of $20\,000 \times g$ for 20 min at 25 °C. A fixed angle rotor of 26° was used. The centrifuge was a *Hermle Z 36 HK* and the settings were "4 acceleration" and "0 deceleration". During deceleration, the brakes were inactive in order not to disturb the distribution pattern. The resulting deceleration time was 17 min. For more details on the preparation refer to appendix 6.2.

Observations

After centrifugation, both samples showed a broad distribution along the tube axis. This confirms the correct setup of the medium density. As found before under the given centrifugation conditions, the distributions show a layered structure. These layers, or bands, are thick and well separated under physiological conditions. In an environment of low osmotic concentration, more layers are formed. Compared to the control sample, they are thinner and less separated, see Fig. 3.17.

Fig. 3.17: Percoll layering patterns after centrifugation under equal conditions. Left, the Percoll medium has an osmolality of 300 mosmol/kg (control), on the right it is 150 mosmol/kg (hypotonic), and the density medium was adjusted. The layers are higher in number, thinner and less separated.

3.12 Sedimentation Distribution of Fixed RBCs

Red blood cells possess a high shape deformability that allows an effective interchange of nutrients with the endothelium, enhances hydrodynamic flow through capillaries and plays an important role in interaction and clustering [14, 34, 63–65]. This characteristic can be suppressed by fixation. Consequently all elastic properties advantageous for capillary flow in the circulatory system are lost. In this section, we used RBCs fixed with glutaraldehyde to study the influence on the band structure.

Experimental Methods

Three experiments have been carried out. One experiment is presented here, two experiments with altered conditions can be found in the appendix 6.3. Fresh venous blood of a healthy donor was collected into an EDTA-tube. In order to isolate RBCs, an aliquote of 1 ml was washed in PBS three times at $1700\times g$ for 5 min.

After washing, cells were resuspended homogeneously in PBS to obtain a hematocrit of around 50%. A volume of 600 μl of the suspension was carefully pipetted to 6 ml of 1% glutaraldehyde solution. The flow velocity was kept low to avoid shear deformation. Afterwards, the sample was incubated for 20 min on a tube roller at room temperature. Next, RBCs were isolated by washing three times at $1700\times g$ for 5 min in 11 ml PBS and resuspended in PBS to restore the previous hematocrit. Since during fixation the osmolality is increased, cells shrink and the density increases. Therefore a percoll medium was density matched. Finally, 600 μl of the suspension were homogeneously distributed in it. The sample was centrifuged at a chamber temperature of 25°C and $20\,000\times g$ for 20 min.

Observations

Fig. 3.18 shows a sample of cells fixed with glutaraldehyde and a control. Both tubes were centrifuged under the same conditions. The density of the medium for fixed cells was matched. The distribution of fixed cells shows a higher number of thinner bands rendering the distribution more homogeneous. Also, the cells appear in a darker red color.

Discussion

The increase in cell density is a known side effects of the fixation process [66,67]. The pH, osmolality and centrifugation conditions were equal between the treated sample and the control. A variation in osmolality within a certain range has no significant effect on the banding formation as previous experiments show 3.11.1. After fixation, blood samples were washed. In contrast, the control were not and therefore contain plasma. However the presence of plasma or other blood constituents has been found to have no significant effect on the distribution of RBCs previously 3.8. Overall we

Fig. 3.18: Images from a control sample, left, and RBCs fixed with glutaraldehyde, right, after centrifugation at 25°C and $20000\times g$ for 20 min. The density medium for fixed cells was adjusted to match the average cell density while all other conditions are equal. Fixed cells appear darker. The structure built by fixed cells shows significantly more and thinner bands compared to the control. Hence, the distribution appears more homogeneous.

can conclude, that the elastic properties of the cell membrane play an important role in band formation.

Erythrocytes fixed with glutaraldehyde show a significant decrease in band thickness and increase in homogeneity of their distribution in a Percoll gradient. Since the deformability is drastically decreased, the ability to form compact aggregates is, too [66, 68]. Accordingly, fixed cells might not form rouleaux shaped agglomerates. Assuming the observed band pattern formation is influenced by coagulation, rouleaux formation plays an important role in the emergence of anisopygmic spatially discretized bands.

3.13 Western Blotting

In western blotting, proteins are resolved on sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamid gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) gels and transferred to a membrane under the influence of an electric current. Other blotting procedures are southern blotting for the transfer of nucleic acids from agarose gels to a membrane through capillary action, as well as northern blotting for RNA [69]. No detailed description of the procedure will be provided. Preparation and conduct of the gel electrophoresis, blocking, antibody incubation, and imaging were carried out by Giampaolo Minetti and assistants in Pavia, Italy. For more information on western blotting please refer to further literature like Yang et al. [70] and Kurien et al. [69]. Western blotting was used to investigate, if the increased homogeneity in a hypotonic medium (3.11.3) and the redistribution after extraction (3.6) can be quantified by measuring the protein 4.1a to 4.1b ratio, an aging marker. Cell density is proportional to cell age, see section 2.1.

3.13.1 Experimental Methods

Samples for western blotting were extractions from red blood cell distributions in Percoll gradients. After cell collection, the sample was washed in isotonic buffer. Afterwards, several steps are involved in the western blotting procedure. Those are the sample preparation, gel electrophoresis, blotting, washing and antibody incubation, exposure, and quantification.

Sample preparation

Cell lysates were used for western blotting. The adjustment of the extracts protein concentration is important to ensure an equivalent basis for sample comparison [70]. In our case, the volumetric cell concentration was easily accessible and used for adjustment.

Blood sample buffers were made by dilution of homemade 10 times concentrated PBS or KCl solutions. For more details on the buffer constitution refer to the appendix, section 6.5. EGTA solution was made as follows. First, 0.1 molar EGTA was prepared by solving 1.14 g in Milli-Q water to a total volume of 30 ml. For that, a beaker was filled to around 70% of the final volume and the EGTA added. The mixture was white, opaque and cloudy. The beaker was placed on a hot plate. A magnetic stirrer was used. The pH was monitored using a pH-Meter. Initially, the pH was 2.7. It was increased by dropping 10 molar NaOH. At pH 7.8, the mixture turned transparent indicating that the EGTA was dissolved. The pH was further increased to 8.0. Finally, the volume was topped to the final. All buffer ingredients were added to 150 ml of Milli-Q water in a beaker. The mixture was placed on a hot plate and stirred. Then, the volume was adjusted close to 250 ml in a volumetric flask. The mixture was placed back into the beaker and the pH

monitored. Around 1ml of 10M NaOH was added to adjust the pH to 7.4. A stock of 10 times hypotonic buffer was prepared by diluting the 10 times isotonic buffer to 62.7%. All buffers were filtered using a 0.2 μm polyethersulfone membrane.

Isotonic Percoll media of matching density were prepared, see section 3.11.2, buffered with the same buffer used for the respective blood samples. For more information of the preparation refer to section 6.2. Centrifugation was carried out and samples collected. Specific methods are explained in the following sections.

A blotting sample buffer was prepared in three times concentration. It contained 50 mM Tris-HCl with a pH of 6.8, 5% SDS, 5 mM EDTA, 35% (w/v) sucrose, and 0.01% (w/v) bromophenol blue as a tracking dye. The dye makes the progression of protein separation visible. On the day of use, it was diluted to 33% and 70 mM of dithiothreitol was added as a reducing agent for disulfides. After sample extraction into isotonic buffer and washing, the cell count was determined from microscopic images either by eye or using an image acquisition algorithm. Afterwards, the hematocrit was adjusted to 2%. Nine parts of the SDS-Page buffer were added to one part of the concentration adjusted RBC sample. Through incubation at 60°C for 15 min cells were lysed and proteins dissolved. The sample was heated to denature higher order structures. This ensures, that the negative charge of amino acids is not neutralized [70].

Gel Electrophoresis

For gel electrophoresis, a *Mini Protean 3* system was used. The running and stacking gel constituents are listed in appendix section 6.5. The stacking gel is more porous and allows proteins to form a thin layer on top of the running gel, also referred to as the separating or resolving gel [70]. After cooling to room temperature, an aliquote of 10 μl was loaded per lane on the surface of the stacking gel.

The voltage was set to 100 V until proteins reached the running gel. Then, it was increased to 150 V. To further separate the 4.1a and 4.1b bands, the gels were overrun by 30 min. The total run duration was 2 h. An image from the running process is shown in Fig. 3.20.

Blotting

"Blotting" refers to the transfer of proteins or nucleic acids to a membrane of microporous structure. Semidry electroblotting was used to transfer proteins from the gel to a membrane. For that purpose, the gel-membrane sandwich was placed between absorbent paper soaked in transfer buffer. Electroblotting is the most common procedure for protein transfer. Since proteins from the SDS-Page are negatively charged, the filter is placed on the side of the anode. An electrophoretic transfer is driven by a homogeneous electrical field between plate electrodes and only the

Fig. 3.19: Illustration of the gel electrophoresis procedure from [71]. Gels are made in cassettes where they cure between transparent plates. The stacking gel is placed on top of the running gel leaving slots for lane filling. The cassette is placed in a bath of running buffer inside of an electrode chamber. Sample proteins in a lysate are filled in the slots. An electrical field, vertical in the figure, is applied which leads to the transport of charged proteins through the gel network. The result is a separation by weight.

Fig. 3.20: Running process at 150 V. The interface of the stacking gel is marked with a pen. In the first lane, multiple bands emerge from the marker sample, prestained *Precision-Plus Protein* by *Bio-Rad*. In all other bands, lightest proteins form a front which is visible as a blue line. When the blue line reaches the bottom of the gel, a 30 min overrun begins.

transfer buffer and liquid in gel and filter paper are used [69].

Prior to transfer, the stacking gel was completely removed to avoid precipitation of the antigens by acrylamide. Electrophoretic transfers were performed using a *Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System*. Two gels were treated simultaneously at 25 V and 2.5 A for 7 min.

Washing, Blocking and Antibody Incubation

A washing buffer was used containing 500 mM Tris, 2 M NaCl, 10 g/l PEG20000, 5 ml/l Tween20 and 10 g/l BSA. Blocking prevents antibodies from binding to the membrane nonspecifically [70]. Our blocking solution contained 5% skimmed milk, 20 mM Tris, pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl and 0.05% Tween 20 (v/v). As a primary

Fig. 3.21: Scheme showing the steps involved in western blotting from [72]. Green labels were added. The first step, electrophoresis, is illustrated in Fig. 3.19. After protein separation, the gel is placed between plate electrodes for transfer onto a membrane (2). Then, the gel is submerged in blocking solution (3). In step (4), the membrane is incubated with the primary antibody specific to the target protein. It follows another incubation with a labeled secondary antibody specific to the primary (5). Finally, the blot is incubated with a chemiluminescent substrate and exposed (6).

antibody, mouse monoclonal (B-11) against human protein 4.1R with a dilution of 1:1000 was used, *sc-166759* from *Santa Cruz Biotechnology*. The secondary antibody was HRP-conjugate goat anti-mouse IgG diluted 1:5000, *170-6516* from *Bio-Rad Laboratories*. Immunodetection involved incubation with equal parts of peroxide and luminol *Amersham ECL* reagents for 3 min.

3.13.2 Image Analysis Algorithm

The membrane was placed in the *ChemiDoc XRS+* by *Bio-Rad Laboratories* where it was illuminated. If all preparation was successful, the chemiluminescent intensity of the dye luminol is proportional to the amount of protein in each band. The raw camera images provide a resolution of 520×696 px² which corresponds to 350 ppi and are stored in a ".scn"-file with a depth of 16 bit. Before our improvements, the workflow included an upscaling via interpolation and conversion into a 8 bit intensity space. This lead to a loss of information and pixel saturation. A new algorithm was designed to work with the raw camera data. The ".scn"-files were read using the Bio-Formats library [73].

The image processing algorithm is illustrated in Fig. 3.22. Images were recorded with a set of increasing exposure times. To select the best, each image is checked for saturated pixels. The image with highest contrast is chosen which contains no saturated pixels. Horizontal and vertical image profiles are used to determine the central position of both bands in each lane and the intermediate positions between different lanes. Based on those values, each lane is cut out. The orientation of every lane with respect to the horizontal image axis is measured. After alignment, intensity profiles are extracted for each row and column. Percentiles of 5 % and 95 % are determined, and the resulting curves are used to compute an outer edge. A double Gaussian is fitted to vertical profiles, orthogonal to the band extension. For each position, a separation location is determined from the resulting distribution function. Then, an edge is derived from those locations, to separate bands. The intensity is integrated over both protein band areas, which are enclosed by the determined edges. Finally, the protein ratio is computed from the accumulated intensity values. For a detailed explanation of the image analysis algorithm see section 6.6 in the appendix.

Fig. 3.22: Scheme of the image analysis algorithm. The exposure of maximum contrast is selected while avoiding saturation. Each lane is isolated and rotation corrected. From intensity profiles, edges around and between bands are determined. The Intensity is integrated over the resulting enclosed areas. For a detailed documentation refer to the appendix, section 6.6.

3.13.3 Ionic Strength and Cell Age

Experimental evidence for the alteration of the sedimentation band pattern in a hypotonic environment is provided in section 3.11.3. Additionally it was investigated, if the gained homogeneity also reflects in the age distribution at the level of resolution that is achievable with the provided materials.

Oldest Cells under Hypotonic Condition

The cell density was assumed to increase with age [22]. A first experiment on the age distribution studies the effect of a hypotonic Percoll medium on the separation of cells of highest density. As concluded earlier in section 3.11, in isotonic PBS the agglomeration is stronger compared to the hypotonic condition. Hence the densest cells from the hypotonic gradient were expected to show a higher ratio compared to an isotonic medium. In the second environment, an increased clumping would mix denser cells in higher regions and less dense cells in lower ones, respectively, reducing the average cell density or age.

In order to check this hypothesis, hypotonic and isotonic samples were prepared. The cells were taken from venous blood of a healthy donor. The blood sample was split into two equal parts. One aliquote was washed in hypotonic, and the other in isotonic PBS.

Experimental Methods

A 80% Percoll medium of pH 7.4, buffered with PBS was prepared. The resulting osmolality was 300 mosmol/kg. A second medium of 51% Percoll and pH 7.4 was made for the hypotonic condition. The osmolality was 170 mosmol/kg. Venous blood from a healthy donor was drawn and divided into two aliquotes. One was washed in isotonic PBS and the other one in a thinned solution of 170 mosmol/kg, both at $2000 \times g$ for 5 min. The hematocrit was adjusted to around 50% by weight. In each centrifugation tube, 0.6 ml of isotonic or hypotonic washed blood were mixed with 8 ml of Percoll medium. Since hypotonic medium is less dense, an additional amount of the hypotonic was added to one of the tubes to counterbalance an isotonic sample, see Fig. 3.23. As before, hypotonic samples showed more thinner bands. Also, they were shifted toward the bottom of the tube compared to the isotonic ones.

Using a syringe pump and microfluidic tubing, 1 ml of cell suspension was extracted from the bottom of each tube. An effort was made to collect as many of the densest cells in that volume as possible. The samples were washed three times in PBS at $2000 \times g$ for 7 min. Afterwards, the RBCs were spun down and liquid phase removed. PBS was added to the resulting cell pack to adjust the total volume to 1 ml. The cell count was measured for each sample and is shown in Tab. 3.2. Since the extracted volume was fixed, cell counts varied.

Fig. 3.23: Density distribution after centrifugation. Samples labeled with I are isotonic, such labeled with H are hypotonic. The hypotonic cells show more thinner bands and an overall more homogenous distribution. Note, that H_1 contains more of the Percoll medium because it acted as a counterweight in the centrifuge.

Fig. 3.24: Percoll layering patterns after the extraction of 1 ml cell suspension from the bottom of the distribution in each tube of Fig. 3.23.

Sample	I_1	I_2	I_3	H_1	H_2	H_3
Cell Count [μl^{-1}]	88450	32030	33480	102470	80760	112999

Tab. 3.2: Cell counts in the samples after adjusting the volume to 1 ml and measured using bright field microscopy of a Malassez counting chamber. The cell counts varied between samples and were higher for hypotonic.

Fig. 3.25: Lanes from the electrophoretic western blotting. Four aliquotes of each sample have been made and two different gels were used. The above image shows the result for Gel A, the lower one for Gel B. Also, the order of samples was altered to account for spatial differences in the Gel gradient. From Gel A I_2 , second, and I_3 , first, the data was discarded after image analysis due to their strong underexposure and distorted shape.

Two gels were prepared, A and B, and four aliquotes of each sample were analyzed. The sample order to different lanes was altered from gel to gel to account for spatial differences in the gel or field gradients. After exposure, bright bands are visible, that appear dark in the inverted image. We summarize and refer to those as lanes.

Observations

First, the images were analyzed the traditional way by Minetti at University of Pavia. All ratios with the same sample origin were combined and the mean and standard deviation computed, see Fig. 3.26. Two lanes of the isotonic sample were dismissed due to distortion. The average ratio for the isotonic sample was 4.2 ± 1.0 and 3.3 ± 0.5 . Accordingly, the two-sample t test showed a significant difference with $p = 1.3\%$. The image analysis was repeated using the algorithm described in section 3.13.2 and the results are depicted in Fig. 3.27. The values for isotonic, 3.3 ± 0.6 , and hypotonic, 2.5 ± 0.4 were lower and the relative standard deviation in the case of isotonic, too. Also, the difference was more significant, $p = 0.37\%$. With this method, no bad data had to be removed. Further supplementary material is provided in the appendix, section 6.7.

Fig. 3.26: Protein ratios from electrophoretic western blotting. The protein densities were measured using manual image analysis. The last two bars show the mean values and the standard deviations are indicated by error bars. Light blue values come from bad lanes and were not taken into account in the total statistics. The difference between means was significant, $p = 1.3\%$. The data was evaluated by Minetti, Pavia.

Fig. 3.27: Ratios from the same samples as in Fig. 3.26 but computed using the automated separation and integration algorithm. Compared to the results from the traditional method, the variations are smaller and the difference between isotonic and hypotonic average is significant with $p = 0.37\%$.

Discussion

Unexpectedly, the 4.1a to 4.1b ratio was higher for the isotonic compared to the hypotonic sample in both cases. For a better basis for comparison, the number of extracted cells should be fixed. This was impractical with the applied method. Since the total volume of the extracted sample was fixed instead, the cell count varied between samples. As Tab. 3.2 shows, the amount of cells from hypotonic samples was higher compared to isotonic ones. Due to the slight downward shift of the hypotonic distributions the volume density of cells was higher near the bottom of the tube. The shift is most likely due to an inaccuracy in the density matching or osmolality adjustment. It is important to keep the cell count in mind, when comparing the Protein ratios between different samples. A higher cell count means, that potentially the average density is lower as more younger cells are included.

Another effect could be an increased amount of dense reticulocytes in the hypotonic environment. In order to eliminate the influence of reticulocytes, a potassium buffer was used in the following experiment.

3.13.4 Potassium Buffer and Separation of Oldest Cells

As discussed earlier, the cells of highest density might include reticulocytes. In a high potassium environment, reticulocytes show a significantly better separation from the remaining RBC distribution in a gradient [44]. However, this is only evident for an isotonic medium. Therefore, all samples were first centrifuged in isotonic conditions and an effort was made to remove reticulocytes from the gradient. The western blotting analysis was repeated in analogy to the previous experiment.

Experimental Methods

Venous blood from a healthy donor was washed in isotonic KCl or PBS buffer. Ingredients of the high potassium buffer are listed in the appendix, section 6.5, and are based on methods by Sorette et al. [44]. Afterwards, the hematocrit was restored. Standard isotonic Percoll media were prepared, one buffered with KCl and the other with PBS. In 8 ml of medium, 600 μl of each prepared blood sample were homogeneously distributed. A first Centrifugation was carried out at $20\,000 \times g$ for 20 min. The results are depicted in Fig. 3.28. Erythrocytes exposed to the high potassium environment are less dense compared to PBS in accordance with [44]. This resulted in a shift of the distribution towards the top of the centrifugation tube. In order to remove the majority of reticulocytes, the top half, that is 4 ml, was removed using a syringe. The remaining samples are depicted in Fig. 3.29. Afterwards, these samples were washed in isotonic buffer and split in equal parts. Finally, all parts were washed again either in isotonic or hypotonic buffer, suspended in a matching Percoll medium and centrifuged a second time. The results of the centrifugation in isotonic and hypotonic condition for high potassium buffer and PBS each can be compared in Fig. 3.30. A fixed volume of 1 ml of each Percoll medium including the densest cells of the distribution was extracted using a syringe pump. An effort was made to collect comparable amounts of cells and not to disturb the structure. After removal, the images in Fig. 3.31 were made. Samples were washed and cell counting performed. The resulting concentrations are shown in the table in Fig. 3.31. After cell counting, the concentration was adjusted to $2 \times 10^5 \mu\text{l}^{-1}$ and the samples were prepared for western blotting. The exposures were analyzed using the algorithm described in section 3.13.2. The computed ratios are shown in Fig. 3.32. All average values are similar. The ratio for hypotonic PBS is higher compared to isotonic. The difference is not significant, $p = 0.201$.

Discussion

Several observations can be made from the distribution of RBCs. By comparing the results to the original distribution of the lower halves in Fig. 3.29, one notices that the distribution now extends above the meniscus. Since the extraction was carried out carefully, a contamination of the lower half with less dense cells can be ruled out as a cause. A more suitable explanation is the redistribution of lighter cells that were bound by agglomerates in the denser part of the distribution previously. During the

Fig. 3.28: Isotonic samples. Left, three equal KCl samples and PBS to the right. The centrifugation conditions and osmolalities were the same. In a high potassium buffer the density is lower. The amount of cells is higher above the cell free zone then below in the KCl sample. The opposite is the case for PBS.

Fig. 3.29: Remaining lower half of the samples depicted in Fig. 3.28 after 4 ml were removed. The lower half contains a low amount of reticulocytes compared to the upper half.

Fig. 3.30: Images of the second centrifugation. Left, isotonic and hypotonic PBS buffered samples, high potassium environment on the right, respectively. The cell distributions extend beyond the previous meniscus in Fig. 3.29 and are more homogeneous and broader in media of low osmolality. KH appears to be less continuous due to the lower volume concentration.

dynamic processes leading to agglomeration in the given system, clumps of lower density formed statistically. Media of low osmolality cause the distribution to be more homogenous and broader. This is also true for the high potassium condition. The distribution appears to be less continuous compared to PBS but this conclusion can not be drawn due to the lower volume density of cells. The extraction was well controlled as it left clean edges and maintained the cell distribution to the eye. However the method of controlling cell count was the rude fixation of the total extracted volume. Since the position of the microfluidic tubing during extraction and the cell volume density varied, the number of extracted cells was not more then similar.

Compared to the results of section 3.13.3, there is no longer a significant difference between the hypotonic and the isotonic condition. The difference between the two experimental conditions was the removal of cells of low density from the isotonic gradients. Avoiding a contamination of the hypotonic samples with reticulocytes, that contain a low amount of protein 4.1a, could explain the leveling of the ratios.

To summarize, we made an effort to remove reticulocytes, and compared oldest cells from a hypotonic and an isotonic gradient. The hypotonic distribution appeared more homogeneous to the eye then the isotonic one in previous experiments. The

Fig. 3.31: A volume of 1 ml of the densest part of the cell distribution from the samples in Fig. 3.30 was extracted. The resulting cells were washed and prepared for western blotting to determine the 4.1a to 4.1b ratio. The table to the right shows the cell count in the extracted samples after washing of Percoll.

goal was to use western blotting to see if a set of oldest cells is contaminated with younger cells decreasing the average age of the sample. No significant difference was found. Hence, our results do not reflect on the observed differences in heterogeneity. Values for the protein ratios showed a large scattering. Also, the extraction was not controlled for number of cells but for volume. The overall resolution might not be high enough.

Fig. 3.32: Distributions of the 4.1a to 4.1b ratio for the samples removed in Fig. 3.31 determined from exposures of western blots. Whiskers show the 5% and 95% percentiles, box edges 25% and 75%. The central line marks the median, circles the mean. All samples show similar fractions. The average for PBS hypotonic is larger than PBS isotonic. The difference is not significant ($p = 20.1\%$).

3.13.5 Sublayers in Isotonic versus Hypotonic Medium

In section 3.6 the re-distribution of red blood cells from a single layer in a Percoll gradient showed a band structure with multiple layers. An attempt was made to compare cells from this sub-structure by age.

Experimental Methods

A layer from the middle of the RBC distribution was extracted using a syringe pump and microfluidic tubing. For the methodological scheme refer to Fig. 3.7. The extracted cells were diluted with PBS to lower the Percoll suspension density, washed three times in PBS at $4000 \times g$ for 7 min to separate of the silica particles. The sample volume was matched to the original sample volume and suspended in Percoll medium homogeneously. A second centrifugation was carried out under the same conditions as before. In the gradient, the RBCs showed a broader distribution then their origin. This distribution was divided into three regions by height. Using a 1 ml syringe with a long hypodermic needle, 0.8×120 mm, cells were extracted to three parts referred to as the low (L), medium (M), and high (H) density sample. A schematic of the sample extraction is depicted in figure Fig. 3.33. The extraction process is depicted in Fig. 3.34 for the isotonic sample and in Fig. 3.35 for the hypotonic, respectively. The samples were again washed to remove Percoll particles. After that, the volume of each sample was adjusted to 1 ml. An effort was made to adjust the volume accurately by weight. Each sample was diluted in a 15 ml *Falcon* tube in the same buffer solution that was used in the Percoll medium. A dilution is vital for a separation, since the sample medium is initially isopycnic to the cells. In the diluted sample, the sedimentation of red cells happens much faster compared to the silica nanoparticles due to the difference in size by two orders of magnitude.

Fig. 3.33: The distribution of RBCs originating from one layer was divided into three groups by height. These groups were extracted using a syringe and a needle. The samples were filled in 1.5 ml tubes. In order to remove Percoll particles from the density medium, the samples were diluted and washed in 15 ml *Cellstar* tubes. After that, the cells were spun down and the total volume adjusted to 1 ml for cell counting.

Fig. 3.34: Isotonic PBS sample. A layer from the middle of the RBC distribution was extracted, washed and centrifuged a second time. The spatial distribution of cells was broader. RBCs were extracted from three different heights dividing the distribution in a low (L), a middle (M), and a high (H) density group. Images (c) to (e) show the tube after removal of the labeled group from the previous condition.

Fig. 3.35: Hypotonic PBS sample. Cells were extracted from the same height as in isotonic PBS. There was no clearly separated layer. After centrifugation of the isolated cells, they show a broader spread. The cells were divided into three groups by height like in the isotonic sample.

Sample	PHH	PHM	PHL	PIL	PIM	PIH
Conc. [μl^{-1}]	116500	472500	174000	28750	300500	122500

Tab. 3.3: Cell counts in the extracted samples after adjustment of the total volume to 1 ml from the isolated layers after the second centrifugation.

Observations

The samples were again washed and the volume concentration adjusted. In this case it was adjusted to 20% (v/v). Western blotting was carried out and the images were analyzed using the image analysis algorithm, see section 6.6. The resulting protein ratios are shown in Fig. 3.36. The pair-wise differences between mean values were tested for significance. Results are presented in Tab. 3.4. A significant difference was found between the isotonic samples of medium and high density.

Discussion

The difference between the low to the high density sample in isotonic PBS supports the observation, that bands contain cells of different individual densities. No such difference resulted from the hypotonic sample. However, deviations between ratios of the same sample are huge. There are many sources of error. Preparation inaccuracies include the variations in the cell count and the difficulty to extract a comparable layer from the hypotonic sample, which does not show clearly separated bands. Furthermore, there are sources of error in the membrane development as well as image exposure and resolution. Considering all those factors, this experiment is inconclusive.

Fig. 3.36: Mean 4.1a to 4.1b ratios. Red bars show hypotonic, blue bars isotonic samples. Darker colors indicate the original layer. Error bars show the standard deviation of each data set. There are twelve measurements per sample. The statistical significance is analyzed in Tab. 3.4.

p [%]	PHH	PHL	PHM	PHO	PIH	PIL	PIM	PIO
PHH	–	37.4	78.6	90.2	60.6	12.9	20.5	43
PHL	37.4	–	59.3	36	72.6	47.2	3.6	10.7
PHM	78.6	59.3	–	83.8	83.9	24.7	17.2	33.7
PHO	90.2	36	83.8	–	62.9	10.9	8.8	29.1
PIH	60.6	72.6	83.9	62.9	–	30.6	8.8	21.4
PIL	12.9	47.2	24.7	10.9	30.6	–	1.1	3.3
PIM	20.5	3.6	17.2	8.8	8.8	1.1	–	68.3
PIO	43	10.7	33.7	29.1	21.4	3.3	68.3	–

Tab. 3.4: Results of the unpaired t-test, numbers are p -values in percent. The differences between PIL and PIM as well as PIL and PIO are significant, i.e. $p < 5\%$, while all differences between hypotonic samples are not significant. The similarity between hypotonic and isotonic samples indicates an extraction from a comparable region in the gradient.

3.14 Percoll Induced Cell Agglomeration

Red blood cells show clumps in an isotonic Percoll medium after centrifugation. Those agglomerates are visible without magnification. Microscopic investigations were carried out to study the occurrence and shape as well as the dependency on the concentration of the Percoll medium.

3.14.1 Basic Observations and a Heuristic Experiment

When erythrocytes come in contact with Percoll, after some time agglomerates can be observed by eye. Fig. 3.37 shows a macro image of bands after centrifugation. Since the sample volume was low, the bands appear unconnected and broken up. Cell accumulations with dimensions in the order of 1 mm are clearly visible. The transition from individual agglomerates to bands is fluent. For the purpose of a

Fig. 3.37: Close up on the RBC distribution in a Percoll gradient after centrifugation. Macroscopic agglomerates are visible and bands are broken up. Note, that the perspective shows not a flat projection from the side but a slight downwards angle.

closer look at the nature of this agglomeration, a PBS buffered isotonic Percoll medium with a concentration of 81 % (v/v) containing 1 ‰ BSA was prepared. BSA was used to prevent cell shape reconfigurations upon contact with glass surfaces. A sample of 0.6 ml of whole venous blood from a healthy donor was mixed in 8 ml of Percoll medium. Centrifugation was performed at 24°C and $20\,000 \times g$ for 30 min. Besides the band structure of RBCs, a single tiny layer of white cells appeared near the top of the tube below the plasma phase. Samples of 50 μl were taken from the lymphocyte layer and an erythrocyte band. Afterwards, the sample volume was released onto a glass slide as a droplet. The droplet spread out introducing a radial flow. Bright field images were taken while distancing from the center using a 20 \times objective. The images are presented in Fig. 3.38. As the radial distance increases, the agglomerates shrink. That means the number of cells per agglomerate decreases. Cells bind in rouleaux formations. Furthermore, at locations close to the edge of the droplet, cells occur individually and agglomerates are rare. The most obvious cause of this loosening of bonds is the radial flow. If shear forces during the dispersion of the droplet are the origin, the binding forces that lead to agglomeration in percoll can be considered relatively weak.

3.14.2 The Dependency on Percoll Concentration

The previous section describes qualitative observations of the agglomeration of red blood cells in a Percoll medium. As a next step, we take a look at a method of

Fig. 3.38: Microscopic Images from the surface of the glass slide. The distance from the droplet center increases from left to right. Agglomerates break up due to the radial flow. Furthermore, they show a clear rouleaux configuration.

quantification that allows an investigation of the dependency of agglomerates, more precisely, their size and number, on the concentration of Percoll. This concentration simply translates into a volumetric density of silica nanoparticles.

Experimental Methods

Three drops of blood were collected from a healthy donor by finger prick and suspended in 1 ml of PBS buffer solution in a 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube. The sample was carefully mixed and centrifuged at 1300 g for 4 min. Afterwards, 5 μl of the bottom phase of red blood cells were collected using an Eppendorf pipette. The sample was resuspended in 1 ml of PBS and distributed homogeneously. Consequently, the sample had a hematocrit of 5 ‰.

Isotonic Percoll media of different concentrations were prepared. First, a mixture of 90% Percoll stock suspension and 10% of 10 \times concentrated PBS buffer were made. Due to the dilution of the buffer, it was isotonic and the pH was 7.4. From that medium, 30% to 80% dilutions in PBS buffer were made in a 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube. The blood sample volume was taken into account. To 900 μl of a 1.11 \times concentrated medium, 100 μl of the 5 ‰ blood sample were added giving the desired concentration. Accordingly, the hematocrit was 0.5 ‰. The resulting suspension constitutions are documented in Tab. 3.5. It also shows the medium density, which was computed following Eqn. (3.2). The density of the Percoll stock suspension is 1.131 g/ml and of PBS around 1.007 g/ml.

$$\rho_{\text{medium}}(\text{conc}) = [(1.131 \times 0.9 + 1.07 \times 0.1) \times \text{conc} + (1 - \text{conc}) \times 1.007] \text{ g/ml} \quad (3.2)$$

For microscopy, *ibidi* μ -Slide with 18 wells, a well diameter 5 mm and a volume per well of 30 μl were used. The well was completely filled with aliquotes of the homogeneous cell suspensions and the wells were closed and sealed collectively using a cover glass. Since the density of the 80% concentrated medium of 1.101 g/ml is close to the average cell density, the sedimentation rate was slow. Therefore, the

Concentration [%]	30	50	60	70	80
90 % Percoll [μl]	300	500	600	700	800
PBS Buffer [μl]	600	400	300	200	100
5 ‰ RBC Suspension [μl]	100	100	100	100	100
Medium Density [g/ml]	1.0424	1.0659	1.0777	1.0895	1.1013

Tab. 3.5: Sample constitutions. The concentration refers to the fraction of 90 % of stock Percoll suspension contained in the final medium. In the calculation of the density, buffer densities were taken into account, see Eqn. (3.2).

filled μ -Slide was stored for 24 h at room temperature prior to imaging. Afterwards, the slide was placed under the microscope, a *Nikon Eclipse TE200* equipped with *The Imaging Source DMK 33UP5000*, and two bright field images were taken per well close to its center but from different locations. The focal plane was adjusted to the bottom of the well.

Image Analysis Algorithm

The images showed agglomeration or clustering besides a number of individual cells. An automated image analysis algorithm was developed and used to measure the projection area of each agglomerate. In order to quantify the amount of agglomeration at various Percoll concentrations, a statistical analysis was carried out. The bright field images show a projection of agglomerates on the focal plane. An effort was made to isolate individual regions of those projections. This is equivalent to drawing a border around each connected region, that appears darker compared to its surroundings due to absorption of light in the cells. This method yields several limitations in finding reasonable quantifiers for agglomeration. First, overlaps of separate agglomerates in the z-direction will be counted as one. Also, the same effect appears, if two agglomerates end up very close to each other on the glass surface. Those events are more likely with increasing volume concentration ρ of cells and increasing height of the column. During sedimentation, all cells in the entire volume sediment to the bottom surface such that the total amount of cells translates into a surface concentration σ , see Eqn. (3.3). It is proportional to the column height h . In this setup, we used an approximate cell count of $5000 \mu\text{l}^{-1}$ which corresponds to $\sigma \approx 7600 \text{mm}^{-2}$.

$$\sigma = \frac{\rho \times V}{A} = \rho \times h \quad (3.3)$$

Due to agglomeration, the number of connected regions on the image will be a fraction of this expected number. The experimental and equal starting point is a homogeneous distribution of cells. It was observed, that the agglomerates are weak when exposed to shear forces. That implies, after mixture the cells can be considered separate. Accordingly, the clumping process must occur during sedimentation.

Since for two cells the probability of forming a bond depends on their distance, the concentration plays an important role. Furthermore, a larger height of the column leaves more time for the dynamic process of approach and interaction. Overall, the concentration and well geometry must be carefully selected and matched to create suitable conditions for quantification.

The implemented acquisition is limited to connected regions of the projection of cell agglomerates. In the following, we will refer to those simply as agglomerates. Given the right conditions, as discussed in the previous paragraph, we assume the statistics on regions to translate to actual agglomerates giving an appropriate tool of indirect quantification. Also, we will refer to single cells as agglomerates with one member. In this statistical approach, two quantities were measured. The surface area and the fraction of agglomerates with multiple members. A custom image processing algorithm was developed which allowed for task specific optimization. It involves several steps, that are described in detail in the appendix, 6.8. An Example of the image processing is given in Fig. 3.39. First, a coarse isolation is performed in the gradient domain. Working with intensity derivatives makes the segmentation independent of the absolute exposure. The resulting projection regions contains multiple agglomerates. In a second step, a finer isolation is established using a local threshold in the intensity domain. The area of each agglomerate is measured, including individual cells. For each Percoll concentration, the probability density function of the distribution of projection areas was computed.

Fig. 3.39: Example of the steps involved in the agglomerate isolation algorithm. From the source image, a gradient magnitude is calculated by applying a Sobel filter. A binary map is computed using several morphological operations. The blurred regions marked in the source image in blue disappear. For each connected region, the center of mass is marked by a blue star. Those regions may contain several agglomerates. By exploitation of a locally adaptive intensity threshold, single agglomerates are isolated. Red rectangles mark the bounding box around each region, and the refined subdivision into individual agglomerates is visualized with green rectangles.

3.14.3 Observations and Discussion

Cropped microscope images in Fig. 3.40 show a region of the well bottom after 24 h of sedimentation. While at 30% (v/v) mainly individual cells are present, the size and number of multi cell agglomerates increases. Also, cells appear to bind more compactly, such that the surface density of cells in a projection increases. While at 50% erythrocytes are in contact, they still show a flat orientation. On the other hand, at 80%, the orientation appears to be more upright. This is a possible explanation for the increased density inside of agglomerates. However, these are only visual observations. The quantification is discussed in the following. The distri-

Fig. 3.40: Cropped microscope images of the well bottom after 24 h sedimentation at $1 \times g$ in isotonic Percoll media of different concentrations. One total image covers an area of approximately 1.15 mm^2 . Agglomerates become larger and more compact as the Percoll concentration increases. Also, unfocused regions appear as the difference in density between cells and medium decreases.

butions of the agglomerate area is shown in Fig. 3.41. Tab. 3.6 lists the total number of cells that were included in the statistics. The probability density function (pdf) was computed using kernel density estimation [74]. All densities show a clear main peak around $28.2 \mu\text{m}^2$ with a standard deviation between concentrations of $0.8 \mu\text{m}^2$. This projection area correlates with an equivalent circle diameter of $6.8 \mu\text{m}$. While single cells appear mostly flat on the glass surface the orientation might vary. A different orientation causes a reduction of the projection area. Taking this variations into account, the equivalent value matches the diameter of the discocyte shaped RBC well [14]. For concentration up to 60%, more peaks around $56 \mu\text{m}^2$ are present. Those can be assigned to agglomerates of two cells. While this second peak is close to the expected value of twice the main peak position for 30%, there is a shift towards smaller values for higher concentrations. This shift indicates a decrease of the distance between cells imposed by an increase in the binding force. This phenomenon matches the observation of an increase of cell density in agglomerates with the concentration.

An area threshold was defined at $1.5 \times 28 \mu\text{m}^2 = 42 \mu\text{m}^2$ to separate single cells from multi cell agglomerates. From all area values below that threshold, the standard deviation average over all distributions was $5.4 \mu\text{m}^2$. Consequently, we can denote the single cell area as $28(5) \mu\text{m}^2$ and the corresponding equivalent diameter as

$6.8(6) \mu\text{m}^2$. The separation by the 150% threshold makes it possible to compute the fraction of multi cell agglomerates among all, including single cells. The distributions are additionally depicted as box plots in Fig. 3.42. The mean and median values are strictly increasing and medians are significantly different according to the estimation in Eqn. (6.12). The figure also includes the fraction of agglomerates. It is the number of agglomerates with an area greater $42 \mu\text{m}^2$ divided by the total number of agglomerates given in Tab. 3.6. It increases from 33 % to 59 %.

Fig. 3.41: Estimated probability density of the agglomerate projection area for different concentrations of Percoll (v/v). The area was measured from microscopic captures using an image analysis algorithm. All distributions show a main peak at $28.2(8) \mu\text{m}^2$ with an average standard deviation of $5.4 \mu\text{m}^2$. The peak height and area decreases with increasing concentration. Additional peaks are present for 30 %, 50 % and 60 % around $56 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Fig. 3.42: Boxplots of the distributions in Fig. 3.41. The central line indicates the median. The bottom and top edges mark the 25th and 75th, whiskers the 2.5th and 90th percentiles. Notches indicate the estimated 95 % confidence interval according to Eqn. (6.12) in the appendix. Circles mark the mean values. Red bars show the fraction of agglomerates, blue bars the fraction of single cells. Median, mean and fraction are strictly increasing with concentration. Medians differ significantly.

Concentration [%]	30	50	60	70	80
Number of Agglo.	4428	5147	3056	2756	2773

Tab. 3.6: The total number of connected projection regions referred to as agglomerates for different Percoll concentrations. It combines the counts from two images each covering an area of 1.15mm^2 in the focal plane. Single cells are included.

3.15 Conclusive Discussion

Several observations of alterations in the RBC sedimentation distribution under different conditions and influences can be explained assuming aggregation to be the key mechanism responsible for band formation. The interpretations of experimental observations in the list below are indicators for this mechanism.

- The layer extraction and recentrifugation revealed that cells are not at their individual isopycnic position after centrifugation in presence of the total sample. They form sub-bands after isolation. This ambiguity can be explained with help of the equilibrium conditions in the theoretical part of this work. Furthermore, it is a sign of aggregation which was also suspected by Lutz et al. [25].
- Fixed cells are rigid and do not form compact aggregates. Rouleaux formation depends on shape and deformability [34].
- Cells in a hypotonic condition undergo a swelling and a loss of deformability. The exclusion volume is significantly reduced by the spherical shape in the depletion model and rouleaux formation is suppressed.
- Upon activation of the Piezo1 or Gárdos channel activity, the resulting K^+ outflux potentially leads to dehydration, a loss of membrane elasticity and the ability to aggregate.
- Trypsin decreases surface charges and is known to increase aggregation [57]. In physiological conditions no difference to the control distribution was found. When stored, cells become nutrient deficient and loose deformability as well as the ability to aggregate [50, 58–61]. Stored samples generally showed a more homogeneous distribution, the control more then trypsinized cells. A difference between the samples is the change in the electric membrane potential. This could explain more pronounced band formation in trypsinized cells after storage.

Furthermore, it was demonstrated, that cells undergo aggregation in a Percoll medium. It is characterized by rouleaux formation and the extent increases with concentration. Therefore, the aggregation in a Percoll gradient is evident.

Among the experimental observations, there are contraindications for an underlying heterogeneity of intrinsic cell properties to be the cause of band formation as listed below.

- Isotonic distributions from the same centrifugation conditions and sample concentrations do not match for different initial cell distributions, namely topped and mixed. Intrinsic properties in question would have to depend on sedimentation dynamics.

- The intrinsic properties in question had not to be linked to the resting shape, as demonstrated with fixed samples.
- Cells had to loose intrinsic heterogeneity in hypotonic solutions.
- Distributions strongly depend on centrifugation conditions, like the tube angle, volume and centrifugal force. Those factors had to influence intrinsic properties in question.
- A single band from a cell population redistributes after isolation by forming multiple bands. Distributions narrow and band count decreases when samples are combined. If the distribution depends on the presence of the cell population, so intrinsic properties of single cells did, too.

The implications that arise from the observations of this study render intrinsic properties of individual cells as the cause of band formation unlikely.

In an attempt to quantify the redistribution of blood cells after extraction from a gradient and the differences in homogeneity between hypotonic and isotonic samples western blotting was carried. The goal was to determine the ratio of protein 4.1a to 4.1b as a measure for cell age which is related to cell density. Among oldest cells we suspected a contamination with dens reticulocytes in first results. By using a high potassium buffer and removing half of the cells with lower density we made an effort to separate reticulocytes and correct results of band densitometry. After this adjustment, the protein ratios leveled out. This indicates, that the previous assumptions were true. Besides from that, only one result showed a significant difference between samples. It suggests, that cells from one band differ significantly in age. However, the sources of error are many and therefore the significance does not allow any conclusions. The sample extraction was not controlled well enough and the resolution of the blotting and imaging procedure is not high enough as the data scattering alone shows.

More experiments should be conducted to show the direct linkage of the explored biochemical conditions to RBC aggregation. Microscopy on aggregation in Percoll medium could be carried out in hypotonic solution, after storage, and after treatment with different drugs. Additionally, single cell force measurements using atomic microscopy to measure forces [34] or shear flow relaxation measurements by means of absorbance [35] could be employed for various suspension compositions in Percoll.

4 Numerical Investigations

In this section we want to discuss a theoretical model to simulate possible forces acting on a RBC during centrifugation. We deduce conditions that lead to the formation of agglomerates and their stability in the equilibrium distribution after centrifugation. So far we have observed, that the distribution is characterized by bands made up of cell agglomerates. Furthermore, we assume the agglomeration is mainly caused by the presence of Percoll, i.e. the presence of silica nanoparticles, see chapter 3.14. The redistribution of samples of different locations in the gradient showed, that the cell arrangement in the supposed equilibrium state is not isopycnic with respect to individual cells.

4.1 Equations of Motion

In the non-inertial reference frame of the centrifugation tube, forces on a single sedimenting cell are the centrifugal and the Coriolis force, hydrodynamic forces including volumetric displacement and friction, as well as interaction forces. The latter are wall collisions and complex interactions with nanoparticles or other cells present in the suspension. Gravitational forces can be neglected because the centrifugal acceleration is much larger. Further derivations are represented in cylindrical coordinates (λ, φ, z) with unit vectors $\hat{\lambda}$, $\hat{\varphi}$ and \hat{z} .

Pseudo Forces

In a first approximation, we will assume that cells are very small compared to radial distance λ and neglect cell rotation. The pseudo forces are given by

$$m_{\text{cell}} \ddot{\vec{r}} = \underbrace{2m_{\text{cell}}\omega (\dot{\varphi}\lambda\hat{\lambda} - \dot{\lambda}\hat{\varphi})}_{\text{Coriolis}} + \underbrace{m_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2\hat{\lambda}}_{\text{centrifugal}}. \quad (4.1)$$

Coordinates with a hat denote unit vectors. We can further simplify these forces by assuming that the relative radial and angular velocity in the comoving frame are small compared to the external angular frequency ω , i.e. $\dot{\lambda} \ll \lambda\omega$ and $\dot{\varphi} \ll \omega$. This leads to the assumption, that only the centrifugal force remains,

$$\vec{F}_{\text{cori}} + \vec{F}_{\text{centri}} = 2m_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2 \left(\frac{\varphi}{\omega}\hat{\lambda} - \frac{\dot{\lambda}}{\lambda\omega}\hat{\varphi} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{\lambda} \right) \approx m_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2\hat{\lambda}. \quad (4.2)$$

Buoyancy

Due to the displacement of suspension liquid, the cell experiences a lift force. It is given by Eqn. (4.3) and is orientated in the opposite direction to the centrifugal force.

$$\vec{F}_{\text{buoy}} = -m_{\text{liquid}}\lambda\omega^2\hat{\lambda} = -\rho_{\text{sus}}V_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2\hat{\lambda} \quad (4.3)$$

Hereby, it is assumed, that the liquid volume is accelerated only by the centrifugal force. The mass of the displaced liquid volume m_{liquid} can be rewritten in term of the suspension density ρ_{sus} and the cell volume V_{cell} .

Hydrodynamic Friction

Moreover, we assume hydrodynamic friction forces to be proportional to the velocity. In order to find a reasonable estimate, we use the Stokes' term with the equivalent spherical radius given in Eqn. (4.4), where η is the viscosity of the surrounding fluid.

$$\vec{F}_{\text{Stokes}} = -6\pi R\eta\dot{\vec{r}}, \quad R = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3}{4\pi}V_{\text{cell}}} \quad (4.4)$$

The velocity vector in cylindrical coordinates is written out in Eqn. (4.5). Here we make the assumption, that the velocity components perpendicular to the tube axis, that are $\dot{\varphi}$ and \dot{z} , are small compared to the direction of the centrifugal force $\dot{\lambda}$. Accordingly, $\lambda\dot{\varphi} \ll \dot{\lambda}$ and $\dot{z} \ll \dot{\lambda}$.

$$\dot{\vec{r}} = \dot{\lambda}\hat{\lambda} + \lambda\dot{\varphi}\hat{\varphi} + \dot{z}\hat{z} = \dot{\lambda}\left(\hat{\lambda} + \frac{\lambda\dot{\varphi}}{\dot{\lambda}}\hat{\varphi} + \frac{\dot{z}}{\dot{\lambda}}\hat{z}\right) \approx \dot{\lambda}\hat{\lambda}. \quad (4.5)$$

Interaction Forces

We will assume simply a fall-off attraction interaction between cells in agreement with our observations. This is satisfied by $\vec{F}_{\text{int}}^{1,2} = \vec{F}_{\text{int}}(\vec{r}_2 - \vec{r}_1)$, $\vec{F}_{\text{int}}(-\vec{r}) = -\vec{F}_{\text{int}}(\vec{r})$ and $\vec{F}_{\text{int}}(\vec{r}) \rightarrow 0$ for $|\vec{r}| \rightarrow \infty$.

Given all assumptions, we summarize the forces in the equation of motion. For a single cell it is given by Eqn. (4.6).

$$m_{\text{cell}}\ddot{\vec{r}} = m_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2\hat{\lambda} - \rho_{\text{sus}}V_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2\hat{\lambda} - 6\pi R\eta\dot{\lambda}\hat{\lambda} \quad (4.6)$$

Since the only force component is in radial direction $\hat{\lambda}$, the cells are resting with regard to the other components. We will assume, that $\dot{\varphi} = 0$ and $\dot{z} = 0$ for all t leaving a one-dimensional problem in the coordinate λ ,

$$m_{\text{cell}}\ddot{\lambda} = m_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2 - \rho_{\text{sus}}V_{\text{cell}}\lambda\omega^2 - 6\pi R\eta\dot{\lambda}. \quad (4.7)$$

Using $m_{\text{cell}} = \rho_{\text{cell}}V_{\text{cell}}$ and $R = V_{\text{cell}}/R^2 \times 3/4\pi$ yields the acceleration in radial direction as

$$\ddot{\lambda} = \lambda\omega^2 - \frac{\rho_{\text{sus}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}}\lambda\omega^2 - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}R^2}\dot{\lambda} = \frac{\rho_{\text{cell}} - \rho_{\text{sus}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}}\omega^2\lambda - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}R^2}\dot{\lambda}. \quad (4.8)$$

Centrifugal and buoyant force were combined into one term. The system of equations of motion for N interacting cells is given by

$$\ddot{\vec{r}}_i = \frac{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i - \rho_{\text{sus}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i} \omega^2 \lambda_i \hat{\lambda}_i - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}^i R_i^2} \dot{\lambda}_i \hat{\lambda}_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\vec{F}_{\text{int}}^{i,j}}{m_{\text{cell}}^i}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (4.9)$$

This system can be simplified with some a priori assumptions. In case, the motion and position perpendicular to the tube axis is neglected, we find $\lambda_i = \lambda$, $\hat{\lambda}_i = \hat{\lambda}$ and $\vec{F}_{\text{int}}^{i,j} = F_{\text{int}}^{i,j} \hat{\lambda}$. This again leads to a one dimensional problem. Also, we can assume, that the distribution of the cell mass m_{cell} is narrow, such that the interaction term becomes independent of the individual cell mass. The derived one dimensional equation system is given by

$$\ddot{\lambda}_i = \frac{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i - \rho_{\text{sus}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i} \omega^2 \lambda_i - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}^i \bar{R}^2} \dot{\lambda}_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{F_{\text{int}}^{i,j}}{\bar{m}_{\text{cell}}}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (4.10)$$

The indexed cell mass was replaced by the average \bar{m}_{cell} . The same assumption was made for the radius \bar{R} . However, replacing the cell density would cause an oversimplification due to the sensitivity of the centrifugal force term in case of $\rho_{\text{sus}} \approx \rho_{\text{cell}}$. This is the case in our experiments, where the Percoll medium is designed to match the average cell density. Moreover, the suspension density is generally a function of space and time $\rho_{\text{sus}} = \rho_{\text{sus}}(\lambda, t)$ and reaches a stationary equilibrium distribution $\rho_{\text{sus}}(\lambda, t) \rightarrow \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda)$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$.

4.2 Stationary Solutions

The equilibrium state is force-free and the cell velocity vanishes. In the one-dimensional equations of the previous section, this implies $\dot{\lambda} = 0 = \ddot{\lambda}$. For single cells, sedimenting in a suspension $\rho_{\text{sus}}(\lambda, t)$, we find the condition Eqn. (4.11) from Eqn. (4.8).

$$\rho_{\text{cell}} = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_\infty) \quad (4.11)$$

Consequently, the density of the suspension liquid at the final resting position $\lambda_\infty = \lambda(t \rightarrow \infty)$ must match the cell density.

In case of a multi-cell system, we get

$$0 = \frac{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i - \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_i^\infty)}{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i} \omega^2 \lambda_i^\infty + \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{F_{\text{int}}(\lambda_j^\infty - \lambda_i^\infty)}{m_{\text{cell}}^i}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (4.12)$$

starting from the acceleration Eqn. (4.10). This equation has multiple solutions. For example we can consider a three cell system $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)$ and a contact force term

$$F_{\text{int}}^{i,j} = \alpha \text{sign}(\lambda_j - \lambda_i) \Theta(l - |\lambda_i - \lambda_j|). \quad (4.13)$$

The notation includes the Heavyside stepfunction and l denotes the characteristic length. Furthermore, the volume of all cells should be identical. Therefore, $m_{\text{cell}}^i = \rho_{\text{cell}}^i V_{\text{cell}}$. In the first case, we assume $|\lambda_i^\infty - \lambda_j^\infty| > l$ for all i, j . The interaction force vanishes. Consequently, the equilibrium condition reads $\rho_1 = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_1^\infty)$, $\rho_2 = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_2^\infty)$, and $\rho_3 = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_3^\infty)$. This means, each cell is at an isopycnic resting position.

Secondly, let $\lambda_1^\infty \approx \lambda_2^\infty \equiv \lambda^\infty$ such that $|\lambda_1^\infty - \lambda_2^\infty| < l$ and $\lambda_1^\infty > \lambda_2^\infty$. Furthermore, the distance to the third cell should be large, i.e. $|\lambda_3^\infty - \lambda_i^\infty| > l$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$. This leads to the conditions

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_{\text{cell}}^1 &= \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_1^\infty) + \frac{\alpha}{V_{\text{cell}}\lambda_\infty\omega^2} \\ \rho_{\text{cell}}^2 &= \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_2^\infty) - \frac{\alpha}{V_{\text{cell}}\lambda_\infty\omega^2} \\ \rho_{\text{cell}}^3 &= \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_3^\infty) .\end{aligned}\tag{4.14}$$

The equilibrium distribution corresponds to one agglomerate from cells 1 and 2 while the third cell is at its independent isopycnic resting position. We find, that the average cell density of the agglomerate equals the suspension density at its position,

$$\rho_{\text{cell}}^1 + \rho_{\text{cell}}^2 = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_1^\infty) + \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_2^\infty) \approx 2\rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda^\infty) \Rightarrow \bar{\rho}_{\text{cell}}^{1,2} = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda^\infty) .\tag{4.15}$$

As a third example, we assume close equilibrium positions $\lambda_i^\infty \approx \lambda_\infty$ with a deviation that requests $\lambda_1^\infty < \lambda_2^\infty < \lambda_3^\infty$, but close enough so $|\lambda_i^\infty - \lambda_j^\infty| < l$ for all i, j . The resulting conditions are listed in Eqn. (4.16).

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_{\text{cell}}^1 &= \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_\infty) + \frac{2\alpha}{V_{\text{cell}}\lambda_\infty\omega^2} \\ \rho_{\text{cell}}^2 &= \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_\infty) \\ \rho_{\text{cell}}^3 &= \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_\infty) - \frac{2\alpha}{V_{\text{cell}}\lambda_\infty\omega^2}\end{aligned}\tag{4.16}$$

This configuration is a single clump of all three cells. Summing the conditions, we get

$$\rho_{\text{cell}}^1 + \rho_{\text{cell}}^2 + \rho_{\text{cell}}^3 = 3\rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_\infty) \Rightarrow \bar{\rho}_{\text{cell}}^{1,2,3} = \rho_{\text{sus}}^\infty(\lambda_\infty) .\tag{4.17}$$

It shows, that the average density of all three cells equals the suspension density at the clump position. Following this principle we can make a general hypothesis about the agglomerate conditions in a stationary distribution after centrifugation.

Conditions of Equilibrium

- (I) The displacement force $\Delta F_{\text{buoyancy}}$ that includes acceleration of cell volume and liquid volume must be smaller then or equal to the total binding force F_{binding} .

$$\Delta F_{\text{buoyancy}} \leq F_{\text{binding}}\tag{4.18}$$

- (II) The average of all cell densities in an agglomerate A equals the suspension density at the average position.

$$\langle \rho_{\text{cell}}^i \rangle_{i \in A} = \rho_{\text{sus}} (\langle \vec{r}_i \rangle_{i \in A}, t \rightarrow \infty) \quad (4.19)$$

It must be noted complementary to (I), that a stationary state requires equality. In experiments this is guaranteed by a hard contact potential as soon as cells collide. In the example, Eqn. (4.12), $\Delta F_{\text{buoyancy}}$ corresponds to the first term on the right, and F_{binding} to the sum over interaction forces.

The condition is illustrated in Fig. 4.1. A binding potential allows configurations where the density of individual cells differs from the surrounding suspension density. That way, agglomerates of cells with various densities can form. Moreover, the equilibrium conditions render the final stationary distribution ambiguous. This is contrary to the sedimentation of independent cells, where the distribution is uniquely defined. As a consequence, if binding occurs, the distribution of cells in a density gradient does not fully represent an arrangement by density. The cell locations are not isopycnic with respect to the individual cell density.

Fig. 4.1: Schematic illustration of an agglomerate in a density gradient. The opacity of blue indicates the density at the given location or of the cell. The forces on the top cell are depicted by vectors. Since the cell density is smaller compared to the suspension the resulting buoyancy term is directed upwards. Binding forces allow the cohesion of a set of cells with densities that differ from the environment.

In the following section, time dependent solutions of the equations of motion are discussed. This is relevant to understand the experiments and gaining a deeper insight in the system. In experiments we can only observe the final distribution. A direct observation of the tubes during centrifugation was not possible and required a great technical effort.

4.3 Time Dependent Solutions

For the case of a constant suspension density ρ_{sus} , the equation for single cells without interaction Eqn. (4.8) is a homogeneous linear differential equation of second order.

It can be solved with an exponential ansatz $\lambda(t) = \exp(-\xi t)$. The characteristic polynomial is written out in equation Eqn. (4.20).

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^2 + \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}R^2}\xi - \frac{\rho_{\text{cell}} - \rho_{\text{sus}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}}\omega^2 &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \xi &= -\underbrace{\frac{9\eta}{4\rho_{\text{cell}}R^2}}_{\Gamma} \pm i \underbrace{\sqrt{\frac{\rho_{\text{sus}} - \rho_{\text{cell}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}}\omega^2 - \left(\frac{9\eta}{4\rho_{\text{cell}}R^2}\right)^2}}_{\Omega} \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

The solutions have the form of a damped harmonic oscillator with frequency Ω and dampening constant Γ . More specifically, the sedimentation trajectory is a step response. In the overdamped case, Ω is imaginary and the curve shows a decay. This always occurs, if $\rho_{\text{sus}} < \rho_{\text{cell}}$, meaning that the cell sinks. Overdamping is also possible, if the initial velocity is directed upwards. However, in sedimentation processes we assume $\dot{\lambda}(t=0) = 0$. Other possibilities are the critically damped and the oscillation case. Oscillation only occurs, if Ω is real, meaning $\rho_{\text{sus}} > \rho_{\text{cell}}$.

Equations, where the suspension density depends on time and location, as well as multi-cell systems are generally not analytically solvable. In the following section, a numerical implementation is presented that allows the investigation of agglomeration during sedimentation.

4.4 Numerical Implementation

In order to solve the sedimentation process in a self-forming gradient for an arbitrary number of cells, the gradient function needs to be studied and formulated.

4.4.1 Density of the Percoll Suspension Medium

A density gradient is formed dynamically in a Percoll suspension during high speed centrifugation. Being of higher density than the suspension liquid, the nanoparticles sediment in the direction of the relative centrifugal force towards the bottom of the tube. This results in a spatially increasing density of the medium. The change in density, i.e. the density gradient vector, is directed parallel to the centrifugal force. Due to the development during centrifugation from a homogeneous suspension of constant density, the resulting gradient is called "self-formed". Here we want to make symmetry assumptions, that equate its direction with the axis of the cylindrical sample vessel. Strictly speaking, this only holds for the case of a swing out rotor.

As reported by *GE Healthcare* [10] and Pertoft et al. [47], the density distribution shows an inverse sigmoidal shape as a function of height h in the tube, see Fig. 4.3. Furthermore, the movement of gradient forming particles in the plane perpendicular to the centrifugal force is assumed to be isotropic. Therefore, the following

assumptions were made.

Assumptions of the Model

- a) The density is merely a function of height and time.
- b) Initially, the density is homogeneous.
- c) The equilibrium density function is inversely sigmoidal.
- d) The transition into the equilibrium gradient is an exponential relaxation process.
- e) The density is unaffected by the presence of cells.

A density function meeting these assumptions is given by

$$\rho_P(h, t) = \left\{ \rho_{P,0} + \epsilon \log \left(\frac{\lambda}{h - h_0} - 1 \right) \right\} \times \left\{ 1 - \exp \left(-\frac{t}{\tau} \right) \right\} + \rho_{P,0} \exp \left(-\frac{t}{\tau} \right). \quad (4.21)$$

The graph of this function is shown in Fig. 4.2. At $t = 0$, the beginning of the centrifugation, we find $\rho_P(h, 0) = \rho_{P,0} = \text{constant}$. The time scale of the exponential transition is determined by τ . Furthermore, $\rho_P(h, t)$ approaches an inverse sigmoidal function in height with the characteristic falloff density of ϵ and the symmetry center at $h = \lambda/2$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$. The physical equivalent of the parameter h_0 is a depth at which the Percoll particles are packed densely. The behavior of the density function for $h \rightarrow h_0$ has no phenomenological analogy and are unphysical. These values are outside of the range of interest. Note, that the average density is $\rho_{P,0}$ at all times, if the symmetry center is chosen to be in the middle of the integration interval. Also, the mass conservation given in Eqn. (4.22) remains fulfilled. For a detailed calculation see section 6.10 in the appendix.

$$\forall t: \int_0^H \rho_P(h, t) A_{\text{tube}} dh = M_P = \rho_{P,0} A_{\text{tube}} H \quad (4.22)$$

4.4.2 Parameter Selection

In order to obtain a realistic gradient shape, Eqn. (4.21) was fitted to the experimental data by *GE Healthcare* [10]. Therefore, a nonlinear regression using iterative least squares estimation was performed. The measurements for 80 % were chosen, the standard experimental conditions include a concentration of 81 %. The fit parameters and the derived simulation parameters are depicted in Tab. 4.1. The initial suspension density $\rho_{P,0}$ was close to the average cell density in physiological conditions. For the simulation, it was chosen to be 1.1 g/ml for convenience. The density spread

Fig. 4.2: Graph of the time and space dependent density, see Eqn. (4.21). The parameters are depicted in Tab. 4.1. From the surface edges, the constant initial density, the exponential transition and the sigmoidal shape are clearly visible.

Fig. 4.3: Left, measurements of the self formed gradient by *GE Healthcare* [10] using colored beads. The curve of 80% is the closest to our experimental conditions. In order to obtain the parameters for the model, the density function of Eqn. (4.21) was fitted. The result is plotted on the right with the interpolated data. The extracted fit parameters are listed in Tab. 4.1.

is around 1.1% of $\rho_{P,0}$. Arbitrarily but reasonably, the symmetry center of the sigmoidal function was chosen to be in the tube center. During simulation, the particle positions are limited to $[0,50]$ mm. We want to define the tube height to be 50mm. For convenience, the height shift was chosen to be $h_0 = -1$ mm. Consequently, the symmetry center is at $h = 25$ mm. The time relaxation process is characterized by the time constant τ . Although experimental centrifugation durations of 20 to 60 minutes are not uncommon, a clearly visible gradient was found after 5 to 10 minutes. Also, a long time development of the gradient will increase simulation time. For those reasons, τ was set to 300s. After 5 min, 63.2% of the gradient will be developed.

Parameter	Symbol	Fit Parameter	Adapted Value
initial (homogeneous) density	$\rho_{P,0}$	1.0967(1) g/ml	1.1 g/ml
density spread	ϵ	0.01224(7) g/ml	0.0122 g/ml
characteristic length	λ	51.75(8) mm	52 mm
height shift	h_0	9.14(8) mm	-1 mm
formation time constant	τ	-	300 s

Tab. 4.1: Fit parameters and the corresponding adapted values for the simulation parameters, see Eqn. (4.21).

4.4.3 Equation of Motion for a Numerical Approach

Based on the simplified one-dimensional system given in Eqn. (4.10) a numerical implementation was established. For that purpose, the Percoll density function from Eqn. (4.21) was used as the suspension density $\rho_{\text{sus}} = \rho_P(\lambda, t)$. Also, the centrifugal force was approximated to be constant along the tube length. In commercial centrifuges, the tube is positioned further away from the rotation axis. For example, the *Hermle Z 36 HK* equipped with the *221.22* rotor features a maximum radius of 8.4 cm and a tube angle of 26° . While the acceleration is $20\,000 \times g$ at maximum radius, it increases from around $14\,000 \times g$ to $20\,000 \times g$ across the tube. Such a change of 40% is not negligible. However, it is assumed to play a minor role in the dynamics of agglomerate formation. Therefore, the radial acceleration term was replaced by the constant maximum centrifugal force, $\lambda_i \omega^2 = \text{rcf}$. For the interaction, a contact force is assumed, like in Eqn. (4.13). A force-free zone $|y_i - y_j| < R$ was added to account for collisions. The prefactor is made independent of the cell index i by using the average cell mass $m_{\text{cell}}^i \rightarrow \bar{m}_{\text{cell}}$. Finally, a coordinate transformation is performed, $\lambda \rightarrow y = \lambda_{\text{bot}} - \lambda$, where y measures the height in the tube, λ_{bot} denotes the radial position of the tube bottom, and H is the tube height, i.e. $0 < y < H$.

$$\ddot{y}_i = \frac{\rho_P(y_i, t) - \rho_{\text{cell}}^i}{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i} \text{rcf} - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}^i \bar{R}^2} \dot{y}_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha \text{sign}(y_j - y_i) [\Theta(l - |y_i - y_j|) - \Theta(R - |y_i - y_j|)] \quad (4.23)$$

This system of N second order non-linear differential equations was treated with a Runge-Kutta method of order four. To do so, we transformed it into a first order system by $\dot{y}_i \mapsto x_i$ and $\ddot{y}_i \mapsto \dot{x}_i$, see Eqn. (4.24).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{x}_i = \frac{\rho_P(y_i, t) - \rho_{\text{cell}}^i}{\rho_{\text{cell}}^i} \text{rcf} - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}^i \bar{R}^2} x_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha \text{sign}(y_j - y_i) [\Theta(l - |y_i - y_j|) - \Theta(R - |y_i - y_j|)] \\ \dot{y}_i = x_i \end{array} \right\} \quad (4.24)$$

The same goes for the special case of independent cells without interaction,

$$\ddot{y} = \frac{\rho_P(y, t) - \rho_{\text{cell}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}} \text{rcf} - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}} \bar{R}^2} \dot{y}, \quad 0 < y < H. \quad (4.25)$$

It was transformed in the same way to Eqn. (4.26).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{x} = \frac{\rho_P(y, t) - \rho_{\text{cell}}}{\rho_{\text{cell}}} \text{rcf} - \frac{9\eta}{2\rho_{\text{cell}}R^2} x \\ \dot{y} = x \end{array} \right\} \quad (4.26)$$

The systems of first order can be generally written as $\dot{x}_i = \dot{x}_i(\rho_{\text{cell}}^i, x_i, y_i, \{y_j\}) \wedge \dot{y}_i = x_i$, while in the case of single cells, the dependency of \dot{x}_i on the cell positions $\{y_j\}$ is dropped.

4.4.4 Implementation in C++

The solver algorithm makes use of the four-order Runge-Kutta method (RK4). The system Eqn. (4.24) is solved by the iteration below. An excerpt of the program code is shown.

```

...
for(cell_i = 0; cell_i < NCELLS; cell_i++) {
    yi = y[cell_i];
    xi = x[cell_i];
    rhoi = densities[cell_i];
    // interaction force
    Finti = 0;
    // sum up forces
    for(cell_j = 0; cell_j < NCELLS; cell_j++) {
        pos_diff = abs(y[cell_j] - yi);
        if( pos_diff < 0.002 && pos_diff > 0.0004 ) {
            if (y[cell_j] > yi)
                Finti += 1;
            else
                Finti -= 1;
        }
    }
    k1x = x_dot(xi, yi, ti, rhoi, Finti);
    k1y = y_dot(xi);
    k2x = x_dot(xi+dt/2*k1x, yi+dt/2*k1y, ti+dt/2, rhoi, Finti);
    k2y = y_dot(xi+dt/2*k1x);
    k3x = x_dot(xi+dt/2*k2x, yi+dt/2*k2y, ti+dt/2, rhoi, Finti);
    k3y = y_dot(xi+dt/2*k2x);
    k4x = x_dot(xi+dt*k3x, yi+dt*k3y, ti+dt, rhoi, Finti);
    k4y = y_dot(xi+dt*k3x);
    x_new[cell_i] = xi+dt*(k1x/6+k2x/3+k3x/3+k4x/6);
    y_new[cell_i] = yi+dt*(k1y/6+k2y/3+k3y/3+k4y/6);
    if (y_new[cell_i] > H || y_new[cell_i] < 0) {
        // out of container, do not change values
        x_new[cell_i] = xi;
        y_new[cell_i] = yi;
    }
}

```

```

    }
}
// store coordinates
for(cell_i = 0; cell_i < NCELLS; cell_i++) {
    y[cell_i] = y_new[cell_i];
    x[cell_i] = x_new[cell_i];
}
...

```

All new coordinates are stored in separate arrays, `y_new` and `x_new`, and the original positions, `y` and `x`, are only updated after the iteration loop. This avoids coordinate changes that depend on the order of indexing cells, when the dynamics should be independent. The interaction force lets the computation time scale with N^2 . As a remedy, cells were sorted by position such that only the neighborhood needs to be taken into account. Starting from the index `cell_i`, `cell_j` was increased and decreased to cover both directions. The summation was only continued as long as the distance between `cell_i` and `cell_j` fell below the characteristic force length. In case of many individual cells, the scaling reduces to N . On the other hand for few agglomerates of a large number of cells each, this value increases back to N^2 . A merge sort algorithm was implemented that obeys a scaling of $N \log(N)$ itself in best, average and worst case while remaining stable. Consequently, the overall scaling is around $N \log(N) + N$ to $N \log(N) + N^2$. Therefore, only for a large number of cells, the sorting algorithm was used. Due to the independent storage of new coordinates, the solutions of both methods were equal given the same initial conditions.

4.5 Results

The interaction-free equation of motion Eqn. (4.25) was solved for a cell of 1.102 g/ml with different initial positions and $T = 300$ s. In Fig. 4.4 shows the resulting curves. After around $t = 0.8T$, the progressions are very close. This implies, that the characteristic time for the cell sedimentation is overcome and, for each condition, the cell only follows the gradient development. Moreover, the final position at $t = 2T$ is the same for each curve up to numerical precision, $\langle y_i(t = 2T) \rangle_i = 2.2518$ cm and $\sigma[y_i(t = 2T)] = 8 \times 10^{-11}$ cm. The equilibrium condition Eqn. (4.11) is met within a deviation of 1.8×10^{-5} as $\rho_P(y_i(2T), 2T) = 1.102020$ g/ml.

Figure 4.5 shows numerical results for single independent cells with different densities between 1.190 to 1.116 g/ml and the common initial position of 4 cm near the tube top. The mean absolute deviation of the cell density from the suspension density is $\langle |y_i(600 \text{ s}) - \rho_P(y_i(600 \text{ s}), 600 \text{ s})| \rangle_i = 5.8 \times 10^{-5}$ g/ml. This isopycnic position indicates, that for long times cells only follow the gradient as buoyant forces become small.

Fig. 4.4: Simulation results for a single cell with density 1.102 g/ml and different initial positions. After 250 s, curves share the same asymptotic behavior indicating an isopycnic position, where the cell follows the gradient. In this example, the average final position at $t = 600$ s is 2.2518 cm with a standard deviation of 8×10^{-11} cm within the numerical resolution. The suspension density at this position is 1.102020 g/ml.

Fig. 4.5: Sedimentation trajectories for independent cells of different densities between 1.090 and 1.116 g/ml in steps of 0.002 g/ml. The amount of blue corresponds to the density. Due to the condition $0 < y < H$, cells remain at the boundary until accelerated away.

Simulations for interacting cells of various numbers were carried out. The cells were positioned randomly and homogeneously in the range $0 < y < H$, using a pseudo-random integral number generator. This distribution corresponds to the mixed initial condition in experiments. The density of each cell was selected from a gaussian distribution with central density of 1.1 g/ml and a standard deviation of 4 mg/ml using the default random number engine class that generates pseudo-random numbers. Both seeds were altered between runs and threads to avoid equivalent double runs. Fig. 4.6 shows an example run for $N = 50$ and $\alpha = 20 \times 10^3 \text{ cm/s}^2$. As curves meet, they combine to the curve of a clump. After one minute, most cells, that is 49, are part of an agglomerate. At around 100s, a clump splits, increasing the total number of clumps to five. This configuration remains until the end of the simulation, $t = 2T = 600\text{s}$. At that time, the gradient has developed to 86%. Since the formation time constant dominates, the configuration is most likely stable. Tab. 4.2 shows the average cell density of each clump and the suspension density at the final position. The deviations are very small which shows a good agreement with the equilibrium condition (II). Most cells concentrate close to the average cell density which is the same as the symmetry center of the sigmoidal density function. The standard deviations are greater than the differences between means for the two largest agglomerates. This means there is an overlap in the density distribution.

A total of 1600 equivalent runs to Fig. 4.6 were conducted for various condi-

N_A	$\langle \rho_{\text{cell}}^i \rangle_i (\sigma [\rho_{\text{cell}}^i] \times 10^5) [\text{g/ml}]$	$\rho_P (\langle y_i (2T) \rangle_i, 2T)$
1	1.10590(000)	1.10596
4	1.10302(200)	1.10305
24	1.10099(393)	1.10098
15	1.10011(238)	1.10010
6	1.09720(115)	1.09717

Tab. 4.2: Final state after $2T = 600\text{s}$ for the curves in figure Fig. 4.6. The agglomerate cell number N_A shows a maximum around the average initial cell density 1.1 g/ml that coincides with the gradient symmetry center. The second and third columns compare the agglomerate mean density to the suspension density at the average agglomerate position, $i \in A$. In this example, the mean absolute deviation is $2.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g/ml}$.

tions. The cell number was increased from $N = 50$ to $N = 400$ and the force strength from $\alpha = 20 \times 10^3 \text{ cm/s}^2$ to $\alpha = 320 \times 10^3 \text{ cm/s}^2$ for each N . The number of clumps in the final state $t = 2T$ was counted. For that purpose, a distance threshold of $100 \mu\text{m}$ was chosen. All cell positions were sorted. If the distance of succeeding cells exceeded the threshold, the number of clumps was increased. In Fig. 4.7, the distribution of this number of agglomerates N_{aggl} in the supposed equilibrium position at $t = 2T$ is represented by a box plot. The median and average number of agglomerates decreases with increasing force. They become independent of α when exceeding $80 \times 10^3 \text{ cm/s}^2$. For $N = 50$, the median remains at 4, and for $N > 50$ at 6

Fig. 4.6: Sedimentation curves for 50 cells interacting via a contact potential with $\alpha = 20 \times 10^3 \text{ cm/s}^2$. A higher amount of red corresponds to a higher density. Most agglomerates form during the first minute. At 100 s, a disintegration can be observed. The opacity of each line depends on the number of cells in the agglomerate. After 10 min, five separate clumps have formed. This configuration is most likely stable as the gradient has developed to 86 %. Further statistics are presented in Tab. 4.2.

with few exceptions.

Runtime was improved by the merge sort algorithm. While the difference was small for $N = 50$ with a drop to 1.81 h from 2.07 h average per run, it decreased by a third at $N = 100$ from 6.33 h to 4.18 h and was cut in half at $N = 200$ from 20.35 h to 10.32 h.

Discussion

In the simulations, the equilibrium condition (II) was found to be valid up to small deviations in the order of $< 0.1 \%$. The sedimentation curves showed an approach from the top as well as an undershoot with a subsequent ascension of cells when centrifugation was interrupted after equal time intervals, see the time dependency experiment in section 3.3. These different solutions were found to depend on density and initial position, see figures Fig. 4.4 and Fig. 4.5 as well as oscillation solutions, Eqn. (4.20). Multi cell interaction simulations showed an agglomeration. The average number of clumps becomes independent of the force magnitude and the number of cells. In our experiments we observed reproducible band patterns. We concluded, that the results are deterministic and as such only depend on the initial conditions, see section 3.1. The stationary number of agglomerates is in agreement with these

Fig. 4.7: Simulations for different numbers of cells N from 50 to 400 and different force strengths α were performed. The number of runs, $t \in [0, 2T]$ each with $T = 300$ s, per condition (N, α) was 50. Furthermore, the initial conditions included a randomly generated position from a homogeneous distribution for $0 < y < H$ as well as a random density from a gaussian distribution with center 1.1 g/ml and standard deviation of 4 mg/ml. The number of agglomerates at $t = 2T$ was counted and the distribution is depicted using box plots. Box edges mark quartiles and whiskers the nonoutlier minimum and maximum, defined by a distance above 1.5 times the interquartile range. Integer medians are indicated by black dots and mean values by red circles. The number of clumps decreases with α and remains constant above 80×10^3 cm/s². For 50 cells, the median remains at $N_{\text{agglo}} = 4$ while for higher cell numbers, the medians of $N_{\text{agglo}} = 6$ do not differ significantly.

observations. In contrast to the definite distributions we see in experiments, the resulting distributions from numerical data show large variations that underlie the statistical process of clump formation. The simulation results that are limited to a low quantity of cells, < 1000 compared to 10^9 in experiments, do not allow a prediction of deterministic distributions. A critical force magnitude was found at 80×10^3 cm/s² from which the results became independent of the force magnitude. Considering a red cell mass of 10^{-13} kg [75], the aggregation force is 80 pN. This value is in a range that is also found experimentally [34].

4.6 Conclusive Discussion

In the theoretical part of this study, conditions for the equilibrium distribution in a density gradient were proposed. These conditions allow various ambiguous solutions in case of RBC aggregation. Numerical investigations of the time-dependent sedimentation and aggregation process with randomized initial conditions in a simplistic model supported the established equilibrium conditions. A very good agreement down to numerical errors was found. Moreover, a statistical insight in the numerical solutions showed, that the final distributions are characterized by a low number of cell agglomerates compared to the number of cells. Further, the average number of agglomerates became independent of interaction force and cell number. Experimental observations of the band structure of RBC sedimentation distributions in Percoll suggest an independence on statistical processes. The resulting distribution is reproducible to the eye given the same initial conditions and centrifugation parameters. Hence, the band structure can be described as deterministic with respect to those influences. Numerical solutions show a statistical scattering in the number of agglomerates and only indicate an asymptotic plateau behavior in the mean or median values. No indication for a trend towards a fully deterministic equilibrium state, like the decrease of standard deviation with increasing cell number, was shown by numerical results. An obvious idea is transferring the number and size of agglomerates in the simplistic model to the experimentally accessible measure of the number and size of bands. The thickness and opacity of bands is highest towards the center of RBC distributions and decreases in both directions. An equivalent observation was made in the number of cells per agglomerate in simulations. The band count in RBC distributions is usually in the range of 10 to 30 in isotonic samples depending on centrifugation conditions and tube geometry. There is no reasonable foundation for the comparison of the agglomerate count to the band count. Merely, the number of agglomerates is in a similar order of magnitude. However, the number of cells was dramatically lower in numerical simulations compared to reality. Therefore the ratio between cell count and band or agglomerate count is very different.

Numerical investigations could be scaled up. A quantity of interest is the amount of scattering of the number of agglomerates in the equilibrium distribution as a function of the number of cells, i.e. the standard deviation of the distribution of all results from a data set of equal framework conditions. A decrease in the distribution width would introduce an agreement with the experimental reproducibility. With this model, simulation runtime scales drastically with the number of cells. Although efficient algorithms could reduce runtime, computation consumed between one and two days per run for 400 cells. An increase to cell numbers of comparable order of magnitude as in experiments is absolutely impracticable. Different approaches would have to be found. Also, numerical investigations could be expanded to multiple dimensions, and membrane dynamics as well as depletion models integrated.

5 Summary and Outlook

Experiments and numerical simulations were done to study the observed band structures of RBC distributions after sedimentation in a self-formed Percoll density gradient. Several physical and biochemical conditions were established in the experiments, e.g. various centrifuge rotor geometries, initial spatial RBC distributions, the extraction of sub-populations with repeated centrifugation, different buffers, the addition of chemicals to modify the RBC shape and membrane behavior, as well as western blotting to distinguish mean cell age of populations. A simple one-dimensional model based on experimental observation, including an attractive force between cells, was proposed to explain the motion of individual cells and agglomeration during the centrifugation process. Finally, the experiments as well as the simulations suggest that the dynamics in the agglomeration process are the major driving force for the formation of the observed band structures.

Experimental Results

Based on microscopic observations, we showed an enhanced aggregation of RBCs in presence of Percoll, see Fig. 3.40. The experimental results can be summarized with the following points.

- The band structure is reproducible given the same experimental conditions, see Fig. 3.1.
- Band formation was observed when placing the blood sample on top of the Percoll medium and when mixing, see Fig. 3.2.
- We find band structures for fixed angle and swing out rotors, meaning for different force directions, see Fig. 3.5.
- An apparent cell-free zone close to the middle can be explained by assuming a vanishing gradient in the self-formed density profile, see Fig. 3.6.
- We extracted bands and did a second centrifugation. A single band shows a broader distribution with a sub-band structure. When two bands with different mean density were mixed, the result was a unimodal distribution with an underlying band structure, see Fig. 3.9. This supports the assumption, that bands contain aggregates of cells with different densities.

- We found no significant difference between the band formations in experiments with full blood versus washed cells. Therefore, the plasma ingredients play a minor role in the band formation, see Fig. 3.11.
- The band formation can be suppressed through activation of membrane ion channels, see Fig. 3.12. Potentially the reason was a decreased aggregation due to morphological changes.
- Cells were treated with trypsin to lower surface charges and increase aggregation [57]. The band formation was similar to control samples without trypsin, see Fig. 3.13 (left).
- Stored cells showed a more homogeneous distribution after 72 h. By adding trypsin prior to storage, the band formation is more pronounced, see Fig. 3.13 (right). A possible reason is nutrient deficiency and a loss of deformability and the ability to aggregate [50, 58–61].
- In a hypotonic environment the bands are thinner and larger in number. The distribution becomes homogeneous, see Fig. 3.17.
- Fixed cells show a homogeneous distribution, see Fig. 3.18. Assumably, due to the increased rigidity, aggregation and rouleaux formation are suppressed.
- Age measurements with western blotting did not show a significant difference in the homogeneity of distributions comparing oldest cells from a hypotonic and an isotonic sample.
- A band was extracted and redistributed. The mean age of the band and sub-populations was measured. A significant difference between cells from the band was found. Results are inconclusive due to a large scattering.
- A concentration dependent RBC aggregation in Percoll was quantified, see Fig. 3.42. Microscopic images show rouleaux formation, see Fig. 3.38.

Numerical Results

The proposed analytical model includes a temporal evolution of the self-forming density gradient of the Percoll medium. The additional crucial component for the formation of agglomerates is a short-range attractive force between cells. The predictions of this model based on numerical simulations can be summarized with the following points.

- The temporal evolution of the enveloping RBC distribution during centrifugation agrees with numerical simulations, compare Fig. 3.3 with Fig. 4.5.

- Agglomerates and bands are formed independent of the initial distribution, compare Fig. 4.6 to Fig. 3.2. The resulting pattern is not reproducible in simulations with random initial conditions, i.e. it is not deterministic.
- Already a weak interaction force between cells is sufficient to predict the appearance of agglomerates, see Fig. 4.7. The required force of 80 pN is in a range that matches experimental findings [34].

Outlook

The presented study collected evidence to support the main hypothesis: Dynamic agglomeration is the basic mechanism for the apparent band formation during centrifugation of RBCs in a Percoll gradient. For further confirmations or rejections of the model, we suggest the following experiments and numerical extensions. If the initial cell concentration is low, the probability that two cells come close enough to aggregate is low, too. Agglomeration events therefore should become less frequent and a band formation prevented. However, the experimental observation is limited as direct observations by eye or with the help of a camera become harder without additional magnification. The numerical model should be extended to two or three dimensions. Then, it is possible for cells to pass each other during sedimentation. This extension allows a prediction of band formation as a function of the cell concentration. The assumed fall-off attraction between cells could be modeled by other short-range interaction potentials.

Future applications might profit from a more homogeneous distribution that is isopycnic to individual cells. The most practical way to achieve this improvement is decreasing osmolality. Exposing the RBC sample to a hypotonic environment prior to and during centrifugation and resuspending it in isotonic solution after extraction is a potential improved preparation method. However, due to the morphological changes and ion exchanges, other cell properties could be affected even altering the distribution compared to an expected homogeneous distribution in isotonic medium.

6 Appendix

Here is an overview over the supplementary information provided in the appendix.

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6.1 Density Matching

For the hypotonic samples, a second series was made. The results of the centrifugation are shown in Fig. 6.1. With a concentration of 51.3%, the matching medium was far from the value in isotonic conditions. The corresponding average cell density was 1.0675 g/ml. Although the density only decreased by 3.1% from the isotonic to hypotonic environment, the effects on the matching concentration and the resulting RBC distribution in the gradient were large. It was concluded, that the density adjustment with Percoll is precise as a large range of dilutions controls a small interval of densities.

Fig. 6.1: Results of the density matching protocol in a hypotonic PBS buffer of 154 mosmol/kg. The swelling has a large effect on the corresponding isopycnic Percoll concentration, compare to Fig. 3.16. The best matching density turned out to be 1.068 g/ml at a concentration of 51.3% Percoll.

6.2 Preparation of Density Medium

This section provides protocols for the preparation of isotonic and hypotonic Percoll density media. In experiments, different buffers or commercial Percoll stock suspensions might be used. The methods are easily transferable to those cases.

Materials

Name	Description	Origin
Percoll	PVP coated silica, pH 8.5-9.5, $\rho = 1.131$ g/ml	GE Healthcare 17-0891-01
1×PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline, pH 7.3-7.5, 280-315 mosmol/kg	Gibco 10010-031
10×PBS	10×concentration, pH ≈ 7.4 , $M_{\text{osm}} \approx 300$ mosmol/kg	homemade
BSA	Bovine Serum Albumin, cold ethanol fraction	Sigma-Aldrich A4503-50G

Other materials include HCl and NaOH solutions for pH adjustment, typically 0.5-5 M, depending on the total volume, as well as whole human blood. The phosphate buffer can be replaced by any other physiological buffer.

Preparation of the Isotonic Density Medium

The following steps are needed to prepare an isopycnic, isotonic Percoll medium for human red blood cells. If the use of BSA is desired, it is practical to add it during thinning with 1×PBS¹.

- a) add 1 part of 10×PBS to 9 parts of Percoll stock solution \rightarrow 300 mosmol/kg
- b) add HCl to lower the pH to 7.4, when undershooting add NaOH, and so on²
- c) thin the solution to 90 % with 1×PBS (optionally containing 1 % BSA³)

Consequently, the constituents of the total Percoll medium then add up as 0.9 of Percoll stock+0.1 of 10×PBS+0.111 of 1×PBS(+1%BSA)+some HCl/NaOH while the volumetric and osmotically active amounts of HCl, NaOH and BSA are usually neglectable⁴. The density of the final medium can be approximated by the following calculation.

$$\rho_P = (0.9 \times \rho_P^{\text{stock}} + 0.1 \times \rho_{10\times\text{PBS}} + 0.111 \times \rho_{1\times\text{PBS}}) / 1.111 \approx 1.113 \text{ g/ml}$$

¹With BSA, the storage duration of a solution is reduced. The 1×PBS stock solution is highly available. It is good practice to store the Percoll medium without any BSA added.

²minimize the total addition of ions to maintain the correct osmolality

³The result is a concentration of 0.1 % BSA in the medium

⁴This was found to be reasonable for larger osmolarities after checking with an osmometer.

By adding whole blood, the density of the mixture is lowered due to the presence of plasma. For a good separation, this solution is used with around 10% of whole blood in the total volume.

Example: Preparation of 50 ml for Storage and Usage with 10 ml Centrifugation Tubes

At our facility, we use 10 ml centrifugation tubes. A larger quantity of buffered Percoll medium might be prepared in stock, 50 ml in this example. The thinning with 1×PBS takes place as a last step in the centrifugation tube.

- a) add 5 ml of 10×PBS to 45 ml of Percoll stock solution
- b) add 5 M HCl, optionally NaOH, to adjust the pH to 7.4
- c) fill 7 ml of the resulting medium in a 10 ml centrifugation tube
- d) add .777 ml of 1×PBS to the tube and mix
- e) add 0.6-0.8 ml of whole human blood to the tube and mix

Preparation of the hypotonic density medium

Lowering the osmotic concentration is achieved by diluting the phosphate buffer solution. The osmolality M_{osm} when diluting 1×PBS with MilliQ is given by

$$M_{\text{osm}} = \frac{V_{1\times\text{PBS}}}{V_{\text{MilliQ}} + V_{1\times\text{PBS}}} \times M_{\text{osm}}^{1\times\text{PBS}} .$$

The same dilution ratio of 10×PBS has to be used⁵. When preparing a Percoll stock medium with a lowered osmolality, the steps are the same as for physiological conditions, but with the 1×PBS and the 10×PBS being replaced by the diluted versions. After pH adjustment, the osmolality will be slightly higher due to the addition of HCl/NaOH.

Percoll medium of 170 mosmol/kg was prepared in the following way.

- a) 4×PBS and 0.4×PBS solutions were prepared
- b) 5 ml of 4×PBS were added to 45 ml of Percoll stock solution; the resulting medium had a pH of 8.27
- c) during pH adjustment, around 0.2 ml 5 M HCl and roughly the same amount of 1 M NaOH were added; the pH was 7.4 and the osmotic concentration 170 mosmol/kg

⁵It will result in the same osmolality, as it is again diluted by a factor 10.

Changing the osmolarity results in a different cell density due to the in- or outflow of water. Therefore it is important to determine the RBC density whenever using Percoll with an altered osmolarity⁶. The dilution of the Percoll medium needs adjustment. For the case of 170 mosmol/kg the matching concentration was found to be 57%⁷. This medium then has a theoretical density of 1.070 g/ml. An amount of 3.44 ml of 0.4×PBS was added to 4.56 ml of 170 mosmol/kg Percoll medium in a 10 ml centrifugation tube. The resulting osmolality was 146 mosmol/kg. Lastly, 0.6 ml whole human blood was added and mixed.

⁶for a good separation, the Percoll medium should have the average cell density

⁷this corresponds to 51% of the commercial stock

6.3 Sedimentation Distribution of fixed RBCs

Experiment A

In a first experiment, fresh blood from a healthy donor was collected in a 50 ml syringe and Li-heparin was added. A buffered fixation medium was prepared. For that purpose, 0.5 ml glutaraldehyde were added to a 50 ml buffer solution consisting of Chur and 1‰ BSA. The medium was mixed by manual rotation and 10 ml were filled into a 15 ml *Falcon* tube. A sample of 1 ml whole blood was added to this 1% concentrated solution. It was carefully placed on top to avoid shear deformation that occurs in flow. The immediate fixation at contact with the solution could freeze the cell in its flow shape. Accordingly, the mixture was again rotated with care. Then, the fixation was given an incubation time of 1 h at room temperature. Afterwards, the sample was centrifuged at $1700 \times g$ for 5 min and the liquid phase removed. The cell pack was topped to the 1 ml mark with the initial buffer solution in order to adjust a hematocrit similar to whole blood, i.e. around 50% (v/v). Lastly, the mixture was carefully homogenized using repetitive pipette flow and slowly released on top of the Percoll density medium.

Experiment B

The blood sample used in experiment B was the same but after a storage time of 20 h. Also, the fixation protocol in this experiment was equivalent to A with the difference of an increased incubation time of 20 h at room temperature over night. Furthermore, the centrifugation was carried out in accordance to the description for experiment A.

Fig. 6.2: From left to right, experiment A control sample, then fixed cells, the same for experiment B. Centrifugation was performed at 32°C at $20\,000 \times g$ for 30 min. Treated cells show a slight discoloration. In both cases, the fixation lead to a more homogeneous distribution with a higher number of thinner bands.

6.4 Layer Isolation

Materials

Name	Description	Origin
Percoll	PVP coated silica, pH 8.5-9.5, $\rho = 1.131$ g/ml	GE Healthcare 17-0891-01
1×PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline, pH 7.3-7.5, 280-315 mosmol/kg	Gibco 10010-031
10×PBS	10×concentration, pH ≈ 7.4 , $M_{\text{osm}} \approx 3$ osmol/kg	homemade
BSA	Bovine Serum Albumin, cold ethanol fraction	Sigma-Aldrich A4503-50G
<i>Chur</i>	physiological buffer, pH ≈ 7.4 , $M_{\text{osm}} \approx 300$ mosmol/kg	homemade
10× <i>Chur</i>	10×concentration, pH ≈ 7.4 , $M_{\text{osm}} \approx 3$ osmol/kg	homemade

Other materials include HCl and NaOH solutions for pH adjustment, typically 0.5-5 M, depending on the total volume, as well as whole human blood.

The centrifuge was a *Hermle Z 36 HK* equipped with an angled rotor, *Hermle 221.22*. The settings were "4 acceleration" and "0 deceleration".

Supplementary Experiment

A centrifugation tube of 10 ml volume was filled with 7.8 ml of a 80 % (v/v) Percoll medium buffered with *Chur*. Human venous blood was taken from a healthy donor and 0.6 ml mixed in the density medium. The sample was centrifuged at $20\,000 \times g$ maximum relative acceleration for 20 min at 25°C in an angled rotor of 26° . The cell distribution showed bands of which several sets of cells were extracted carefully using a syringe pump and microfluidic tubing. All sets of cells were washed 3 times in *Chur* buffer using a 15 ml *Cellstar* tube at $4000 g$ for 7 min. The cell packs were resuspended to restore a sample volume of 0.6 ml. The complete extraction process with all distributions is presented in Fig. 6.3. First, cells of lower density (L_1) and of higher density (H_1) were collected. The samples were centrifuged a second time. The resulting distribution of the set of cells was broader than originally. Therefore it was possible to extract a subset of lower density (L_2) from L_1 and accordingly higher density (H_2) from H_1 . After a third centrifugation, another lower density subset (L_3) of the resulting distribution of L_3 was collected and the process repeated. The cells of L_3 and H_2 were extracted almost completely, mixed and resuspended to restore a volume of 0.6 ml. The resulting sample was mixed with 7.8 ml density

medium and centrifuged under the same conditions. Afterwards, the tube was placed back in the rotor and centrifuged a second time under equal conditions. The total centrifugation duration was 40 min for this sample excluding acceleration and deceleration times.

Fig. 6.3: Density distributions of different sample sets. On the far left, 0.6 ml full blood of a healthy donor. From that, a low density sample L_1 and a high density sample H_1 were extracted. Samples L_2 to L_3 and H_2 were each collected after a further centrifugation under the same conditions. All set of cells show a broader distribution after isolation then in the entirety they were collected from.

Observations

After a subset of cells was centrifuged under the same conditions as the sample they originated from, their height distribution was broader in every of the examined cases. Assuming a weak influence of the presence of cells on the self-formed gradient shape in the given conditions, the broadening in the y -dimension relates to a broadening in the density distribution. This assumption gains validity as the amount of cells in the sample decreases. In the case of L_2 to L_3 the separation and band formation is especially pronounced. Furthermore, the average height remained roughly the same. When H_2 and L_3 were combined, the resulting distribution showed two main accumulations with similar width and position as the individual distributions showed separately. the lower density cells formed more a clearer band structure. The second

centrifugation caused the two main accumulations to move closer together and reduced the distribution widths. Also, the banding substructure of L_3 collapsed.

Fig. 6.4: The cells of L_3 and H_2 were extracted, mixed and re-suspended. The resulting sample was centrifuged under the same conditions, see third image. Afterwards, the tube was placed back in the rotor and centrifuged a second time under equal conditions, see fourth image.

6.5 Western Blotting Materials

Ingredient	Running Gel (v/v)	Stacking Gel (v/v)
Acrylamide 30 %	50 %	10 %
Tris/HCl pH 6.8	25 % of 1.5 M	10 % of 1.25 M
SDS 10 %	1 %	1 %
AP 10 %	1 %	1 %
Temed 1 %	5 %	10 %
H ₂ O	18 %	68 %

Tab. 6.1: Ingredients of the running and stacking gels.

The blocking solution was made of 5 % skimmed milk, 20 mM Tris of pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl and 0.05 % Tween20 (v/v). The osmolality was adjusted to obtain the values

Name	Description	Origin
Percoll Plus	silane coated silica, pH 8.9-9.9, $\rho = 1.130$ g/ml	GE Healthcare 17-5445-01
PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline, pH = 7.4, $M_{\text{osm}} = 298$ mosmol/kg	homemade
KCl	high potassium buffer, pH = 7.4, $M_{\text{osm}} = 295$ mosmol/kg	homemade
PBS hypo	diluted PBS buffer, pH = 7.4, $M_{\text{osm}} = 184$ mosmol/kg	homemade
KCl hypo	diluted KCl buffer, pH = 7.4, $M_{\text{osm}} = 183$ mosmol/kg	homemade

Tab. 6.2: Materials for Percoll density media.

listed in Tab. 6.2 after diluting to 10 %. The constituents of the HEPES-based KCl buffers are listed in Tab. 6.3.

Ingredient	Conc. [mmol/l]	in 250 ml of 10×
HEPES	20	11.915 g
MgCl ₂	1	238 mg
NaH ₂ PO ₄	1	340.25 mg
glucose	10	4.504 g
0.1M EGTA	0.5	12.5 ml
NaCl	12	1.753 g
KCl	120	22.43 g

Tab. 6.3: Constituents of the high potassium buffer. It was based on the protocol of [44].

Fig. 6.5: In this acquisition, two successive exposure series were recorded. Each image was checked for saturation. The saturated pixels are marked red in the figure. Afterwards, the image with the highest contrast but without overexposure was automatically selected. During the second exposure series, the contrast was decreased compared to the first one. For example an exposure of 4s resulted in much less saturated pixels in the second series.

6.6 Image Analysis Algorithm

The membrane was placed in the *BIO-RAD ChemiDoc XRS+* where it was illuminated by ultraviolet light. The photoluminescence intensity of the dye luminol in the blue range is proportional to the amount of protein in each band. The raw camera images provide a resolution of $520 \times 696 \text{ px}^2$ which corresponds to 350 ppi and come packed in a ".scn"-file with a depth of 16 bit. The traditional workflow included an upscaling via interpolation and conversion into a 8 bit intensity space. This lead to a loss of information and pixel saturation. A new algorithm was designed to work with the raw camera data. The ".scn"-files were read using the Bio-Formats library [73].

6.6.1 Lane Slicing

As a first step, lanes are separated by slicing the acquired Western Blot image vertically at intermediate positions. These positions are determined from the average horizontal image profile given by Eqn. (6.1). I denotes the two dimensional image matrix, i counts columns and j rows. Afterwards a moving average filter is applied with a length of 60% of the lane width. This filter guarantees peaks in the lane centers. An example of the resulting mean horizontal profile is shown in Fig. 6.6. After that, a peak detection algorithm was applied to determine the lane center positions and the corresponding intensity maxima. There peak points were used to compute a enveloping curve, referred to as the background fit. By

Fig. 6.6: Diagram (a) shows the average horizontal image profile of the acquired Western Blot. It was computed according to Eqn. (6.1). A peak detection algorithm was used to determine the lane center positions. In order to separate lanes, the intermediate minima need to be located. Hence, a smoothing spline function was fitted to the peak points. The image profile was subtracted from this background fit, resulting in an inverted profile (b). Again using the peak detection algorithm, the locations of the slicing points between lanes were determined. The results are depicted in Fig. 6.7.

means of subtraction, the intermediate minima could be isolated. Through a second application of the peak detection algorithm, the slicing positions could be obtained. The results for the given example are depicted in Fig. 6.7.

$$\langle I \rangle_h[i] = \frac{\sum_j I[j, i]}{\sum_j} \quad (6.1)$$

After lanes have been successfully separated by a vertical slicing, the next step of lane isolation is the horizontal cropping.

6.6.2 Lane Cropping and Rotation Correction

As a first step of lane cropping, the vertical mean profile of each lane slice was computed, following Eqn. (6.1) but summing over the second dimension. The

Fig. 6.7: Lane slicing results. Red lines mark separation edges, corresponding to the peak positions in Fig. 6.6 (b), blue lines the central positions of lanes, extracted in Fig. 6.6 (a), respectively.

resulting profiles are depicted in Fig. 6.8 for each of the example lanes. The vertical lane center position was determined by evaluating the expectation value of the vertical index with respect to the intensity distribution according to Eqn. (6.2). Finally, the image slices were cropped symmetrically around the center $\langle i \rangle_p$ such that the cropped images were square.

$$\langle i \rangle_p = \frac{\sum_i p[i] \times i}{\sum_i p[i]}, \quad p = \langle I_{\text{slice}} \rangle_v \quad (6.2)$$

Next, the rotation of each lane was corrected. That means the long band axes were aligned with the horizontal direction. For that purpose, a centroid was obtained from the cropped lane images applying an intensity threshold. Otsu's method was used for choosing the value that minimizes the intraclass variance of black and white pixels [76]. From that centroid, the major and minor axis of the ellipse of equal normalized second central moment were computed. The centroid boundary, the axis and the rotation angle are shown in Fig. 6.9. Using this method, the orientation ϕ of each band was measured and corrected by means of a rotation mapping and an integration into the pixel grid by nearest neighbor interpolation. The left diagram of Fig. 6.9 shows ϕ as a function of the lane number. It decreases and changes sign close to the middle of the membrane, at lane number 6. It therefore fits to the bow shaped arrangement of bands clearly visible in Fig. 6.7. The rotation corrected image, as shown on the right side of Fig. 6.9 appears straight but shows interpolation artefact. The aligned images are only used in the further procedure to do the band separation and isolation. All intensity data that is processed in the ratio computation is however raw data that was not transformed.

6.6.3 Band Separation and Isolation

Starting from the images of bands aligned with the horizontal axis, the separation and isolation of the 4.1a and 4.1b bands is performed. The goal is to find a closed outer edge around the bands and a separating edge between them. For every column, counted by $j = 1 \dots w$, the image profile $I[i, j] \equiv I_j[i]$, $i = 1 \dots h$ is extracted. The normalized numerical integral is computed using the trapezoidal method formulated

Fig. 6.8: Of each lane slice, separated by the red lines in Fig. 6.7, the vertical mean profile was calculated following Eqn. (6.1) but in the second dimension. Note, that the abscissa spans from 0 to 100 px for each lane and profiles in blue are concatenated in this diagram. Red lines mark the expectation value of the position weighted by the intensity distribution, see Eqn. (6.2).

in Eqn. (6.3).

$$\text{Int}(I_j)[i] = \frac{1}{2\text{Int}(I_j)[h]} \sum_{k=1}^i (I_j[k] + I_j[k+1]), \quad i = 1 \dots h, \quad h : \text{image height} \quad (6.3)$$

Next, the 5% and 95% percentiles of the intensity distribution are calculated following Eqn. (6.4).

$$i_p = \sup(\{i | \text{Int}(I_j)[i] \leq p\}), \quad p \in \{0.05, 0.95\} \quad (6.4)$$

The percentiles are later used to compute the outer edge around the two bands. Moreover, the vertical profile is also used to define a separation point between them. In the process, a double gaussian is fitted to the intensity curve. If existing, the minimum or saddle abscissa of the double gaussian given by Eqn. (6.5) is the solution of Eqn. (6.6).

$$a_1 \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_1)^2}{c_1^2}\right) + a_2 \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_2)^2}{c_2^2}\right) \quad (6.5)$$

$$\frac{a_1(x-b_1)}{c_1^2} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_1)^2}{c_1^2}\right) + \frac{a_2(x-b_2)}{c_2^2} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_2)^2}{c_2^2}\right) = 0 \quad (6.6)$$

Since there are no solutions if the two gaussians are too close together, the separation point s_j is determined by one of two methods. Method A involves finding the minimizer of the the term in Eqn. (6.7). The term is evaluated for different values of x and the minimum is determined using a peak detection algorithm.

$$s_j \equiv \min_x \left(\left| \frac{a_1(x-b_1)}{c_1^2} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_1)^2}{c_1^2}\right) + \frac{a_2(x-b_2)}{c_2^2} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_2)^2}{c_2^2}\right) \right| \right) \quad (6.7)$$

In method B, the turning point defines the slicing location. For this, the absolute value of the second derivative, Eqn. (6.8), is minimized numerically.

$$s_j \equiv \min_x \left(\left| \frac{a_1}{c_1^2} \left(1 - 2\frac{(x-b_1)^2}{c_1^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_1)^2}{c_1^2}\right) + \frac{a_2}{c_2^2} \left(1 - 2\frac{(x-b_2)^2}{c_2^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{(x-b_2)^2}{c_2^2}\right) \right| \right) \quad (6.8)$$

Fig. 6.9: Left, rotation angles of each lane. The angle decreases and changes sign in the middle of the blot. This manifests in the bow shaped orientation on the image in Fig. 6.7. The middle image illustrates the computation of the orientation angle for the first lane. Using an intensity threshold, a centroid is defined, the boundary of which is marked by the green edge. The major and minor axes and from those the rotation angle ϕ are computed. Every cropped lane was rotated inversely as demonstrated on the right side, which shows the first lane after clockwise correction.

Also, a combination of both methods might be used. In this case the average of approximated minimum and turning point is taken.

Once, the separation points s_j are determined for every pixel column, they are filtered to remove outliers using a neighborhood comparison algorithm and a smoothing spline is fitted by minimizing Eqn. (6.9). The value of p must be chosen such that $s(x)$ follows details like bulges and dents in the band edge but smooth enough to reduce the influence of bad data points. Here it is set to $p = 0.01$.

$$p \sum_j (s_j - s(x_j))^2 + (1 - p) \int \left(\frac{d^2 s}{dx^2} dx \right) \quad (6.9)$$

In order to obtain a closed edge around the bands, the percentile lines are also computed for the horizontal profiles. Together with the vertical percentiles the bands are enclosed such that approximately the lowest 10% of intensity are outside. In order to take care of the edges, a gray scale matching is performed. The counter line of equal gray is determined which shows the most overlap with the percentile lines. All data is presented in Fig. 6.10 for two examples. One lane belongs to a sample from the middle of the RBC distribution and was analyzed using method A. The second one stems from the bottom of high density. The RBC age is higher and so is the contrast between bands. In this case, the gaussian peaks are not separated. Hence a combination of method A and B was used.

6.6.4 Intensity Integration and Fraction Computation

The last step of protein ratio computation is the Intensity integration and division. Fig. 6.11 shows an example of the results of the band separation algorithm. The outer

Fig. 6.10: Band separation results. On the left image, method A was used. In case of the right lane, where the contrast difference is higher, a combination of method A and B was carried out. The left sample originated in the middle of the RBC distribution while the right one was extracted from the bottom.

Fig. 6.11: Results of the band isolation and separation of the lanes shown in Fig. 6.7. The yellow tinted regions mark band 4.1a, the blue ones 4.1b. Those define the integration areas in Eqn. (6.11).

edge, referred to as perimeter P , is divided into two regions by the separation line. An integration over the perimeter P gives a value for the background intensity that is calculated according to Eqn. (6.10). The two band regions define the integration areas A and B in the fraction computation Eqn. (6.11).

$$I_0 := \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in P} I(i,j)}{\sum_{(i,j) \in P} 1} \quad (6.10)$$

$$(4.1a : 4.1b) := \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in A} I(i,j) - I_0 \sum_{(i,j) \in A} 1}{\sum_{(i,j) \in B} I(i,j) - I_0 \sum_{(i,j) \in B} 1} \quad (6.11)$$

6.7 Ionic Strength and Cell Age

In the traditional workflow, a separation position is determined manually from one image profile per lane. The segmentation of lanes is based on this threshold. Prior to the analysis, images were converted and showed saturation. Data from this method are presented in the following.

Oldest Cells under Hypotonic Condition

The traditional data acquisition was performed by Giampaolo Minetti at University of Pavia. Figure 6.12 shows image profiles from the lanes of Gel A. One lane contains two layers, one originating from 4.1a and one from 4.1b. Consequently the profiles show double peaks. From these peaks a threshold is defined by which the layers are separated. The intensity weighted areas are then divided. The second lane of I_2 and the first of I_3 were discarded in the analysis due to deformation and large overexposure. The raw results are shown in table 6.4. Also a qualitative investigation of the clipping of the lane images was performed. It shows, that a huge portion of the lanes were at least partially saturated. Figure 6.13 shows the same profiles for Gel B. All ratios and the mean values are depicted in figure 3.26.

Fig. 6.12: Image profiles from the lanes shown in figure 3.25 for Gel A. From the double peak, a threshold was determined and the areas of both intensity peaks computed. Note, that oversaturation of the lane does not show as a clipping in these profiles. Figures were produced by Minetti, Pavia.

Fig. 6.13: The images of Gel B have been analyzed in the same way as for Gel A. in comparison to Gel A, more underexposure has been found and the separation seems to be worse. Figures were produced by Minetti, Pavia.

		Gel A		Gel B		Lane Saturation	
			a/b		a/b		
I_1	723	4.231	I_1	709	3.101	Gel A	I_1 no
I_1	171		I_1	229			I_1 no
I_1	813	3.058	H_1	2425	3.740		H_1 yes
I_1	266		H_1	649			H_1 yes
H_1	2112	3.088	I_2	4410	6.216		I_2 yes
H_1	684		I_2	710			I_2 yes
H_1	1974	3.365	H_2	1246	2.636		H_2 no
H_1	587		H_2	473			H_2 no
I_2	2648	4.321	I_3	2164	4.335		I_3 yes
I_2	613		I_3	499			I_3 slight
I_2	5207	6.152	H_3	2046	3.374		H_3 no
I_2	846		H_3	606			H_3 no
H_2	1160	2.683	I_1	2005	3.469	Gel B	I_1 yes
H_2	432		I_1	578			I_1 yes
H_2	1296	2.926	H_1	2309	2.847		H_1 yes
H_2	443		H_1	811			I_2 no
I_3	3061	6.004	I_2	3416	4.627		H_2 no
I_3	510		I_2	738			I_3 slight
I_3	1782	4.818	H_2	1532	2.901		H_3 slight
I_3	370		H_2	528			I_1 yes
H_3	1221	4.181	I_3	1322	3.424		H_1 yes
H_3	292		I_3	386			I_2 yes
H_3	1228	4.170	H_3	786	3.378		H_2 slight
H_3	294		H_3	233			I_3 slight
							H_3 no

Tab. 6.4: Raw intensity values from the image analysis and derived Protein ratios for each sample. The amounts of Proteins have been computed from the image profiles shown in figure 3.25. A visual examination of the saturation by underexposure was done by judging the clipping of the intensity values in three dimensional surface plots qualitatively, see right. The data was evaluated by Minetti, Pavia.

	I_1	I_2	I_3	H_1	H_2	H_3	I_{tot}	H_{tot}	t -test
Mean	3.465	5.055	4.192	3.260	2.787	3.776	4.160	3.274	$p = 0.0126$
SD	0.471	0.831	0.578	0.332	0.128	0.400	0.911	0.509	$t = 2.74$
C.V.	13.6	16.4	13.8	10.2	4.6	10.6	21.9	15.5	$sd = 0.755$

Tab. 6.5: Statistics on the 4.1a to 4.1b ratios depicted in table 6.4. The bad lanes marked in figure 3.26 were not taken into account for the total statistics. The test of significance was a two-sample t -test. Values are provided by Minetti, Pavia.

6.8 Percoll Induced Cell Agglomeration

An algorithm was developed to determine the size of agglomerates from microscopic images. The image processing steps are documented in the following.

Image Analysis Algorithm

First, the unsigned 8 bit integer gray scale source image is read. Applying a Sobel filter, the gradient magnitude is computed at each point, see Fig. 6.14. The advantage of working in the gradient domain is the independence from absolute shifts and slow changes of exposure. Such variations are commonly introduced by the radial fall off of the light cone of other inhomogeneities in the light source or path. From the gradient magnitude image, a binary map is computed using a global threshold. It is heuristically fixed at 0.35 of the max intensity 255. That way, the first and coarse segmentation is independent of the density of cells and only depends on the amount of absorption and image sharpness. Those parameters are well controlled and reproduced experimentally. The image is morphologically opened removing segments below $4\ \mu\text{m}^2$, holes are filled, and a second removal with a threshold of $17\ \mu\text{m}^2$ is performed. The edges are smoothed and widened by applying a 3 by 3 Gaussian blur filter and a global threshold. Connected regions in the binary map are isolated and an image of each segment is saved separately. An example of this first segmentation is depicted in Fig. 6.15 to the right.

In a second routine, each coarse segment is analyzed and divided into finer ones. Those are assumed to represent individual agglomerates. The first step involves computing a binary map of the segment using its median intensity. This method allows to separate cells precisely from its surroundings. The reproducible inclusion of an enclosing perimeter of the cell free environment in the first segmentation is vital. That given, a median bitmap delivers a robust isolation. An example is presented in Fig. 6.16. It shows, how a coarse region may include multiple separate agglomerates, and also includes a generous stripe of the surrounding area. Furthermore the adequate separation by the binary map is demonstrated.

There are two mechanisms to avoid bad data. First, regions intercepting with the image edges are discarded. Furthermore, in some occasions, unfocused cells appear in the image. This is more likely for higher Percoll concentrations as sedimentation takes longer and not all cells are at the bottom at the moment of capture. Also, at 80 %, some cells might own a density very similar to the medium density causing them to float. If those blurred regions appear isolated in the source image, they disappear in the gradient image, see Fig. 6.14. However if they overlap with sharper regions, they cause a shallow edge which makes a clear separation impossible. This case is illustrated in Fig. 6.15. As a remedy, a false edge detection algorithm was implemented. All pixels belonging to the edge of a region are compared to the medium intensity across the entire region. If the intensity falls below the median,

this region is discarded. The picture on the right side of Fig. 6.15 shows an example.

Fig. 6.14: Example of the steps involved in the agglomerate isolation algorithm. From the source image, a gradient magnitude is calculated by applying a Sobel filter. A binary map is computed using several morphological operations. The blurred regions marked in the source image in blue disappear. For each connected region, the center of mass is marked by a blue star. Those regions may contain several agglomerates. By exploitation of a locally adaptive intensity threshold, single agglomerates are isolated. Red rectangles mark the bounding box around each region, and the refined subdivision into individual agglomerates is visualized with green rectangles.

Fig. 6.15: The segmentation is a process working from a coarse to a fine scale. In this source image 22 regions are detected and isolated. Afterwards, the median intensity of the surrounding area of each region is used for a refined segmentation into 33 parts. The area of the resulting cut outs is measured for a statistical analysis. The region marked in blue shows a darkening by an agglomerate above the focal plane. Such regions are filtered out by a false edge detection algorithm and discarded. The image to the right shows the region edge in blue. A red arrow marks a location, where the intensity on the edge falls below the median gray value across the region. Regions that intersect with image edges are also not taken into account.

Fig. 6.16: The refined segmentation isolates agglomerates from pre-selected image regions based on a median bitmap. The agglomerates that are derived from the coarse region on the left are montaged in the image to the right.

Equation for Notches in Boxplots

The notches give an estimate for the 95 % confidence interval of the median value. The notch width is given by Eqn. (6.12) [77].

$$95\%CI_{\text{mean}} = \text{median} \pm \frac{1.57 \times \text{IQR}}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (6.12)$$

6.9 Sedimentation Time Scales

When cells are centrifuged in a self-forming Percoll gradient, there are two sedimentation processes. Silica particles sediment to form a distribution that results in the gradient and red blood cells move to a resting position. In Svedberg's simplified theory [78], sedimenting particles reach a terminal velocity, when centrifugal and friction force cancel. In case of a friction proportional to the velocity, a sedimentation coefficient is defined as the terminal velocity normalized by the acceleration a_{cen} . Thus, the terminal velocity is given by $v_t = s \times a_{\text{cen}}$. In hydrodynamic theory, a spherical particle experiences Stokes friction. In that case, the sedimentation coefficient is given by Eqn. (6.13). It depends on the excess mass of the particle over the equivalent liquid volume, $m_p - m_\ell$.

$$s = \frac{m_p - m_\ell}{6\pi\eta R_p} \quad (6.13)$$

With the particle volume of V_p , the sedimentation coefficient can be written as Eqn. (6.14).

$$s = V_p \frac{\rho_p - \rho_\ell}{6\pi\eta R_p} \quad (6.14)$$

The sedimentation coefficient measures the time until terminal velocity is reached and hence is a suitable indicator for the time scale until a resting position is reached. In case of red blood cells, the mean corpuscular volume is around 90 fl [75] and the mean density 1.1 g/ml [52, 53]. The equivalent spherical radius is 2.8 μm . According to the gradient shapes from experimental data, we assume the density of the liquid to be 1.08 g/ml. For the viscosity we take the value for the Percoll suspension of 15 mPa s as the nanoparticles are much smaller than the cells. With these values, we get a sedimentation coefficient for RBCs of $s_{\text{RBC}} \approx 2 \times 10^4 \text{ S}$. That means the terminal velocity at $20\,000 \times g$ is around 400 $\mu\text{m/s}$.

For a comparison to the gradient formation, we want to estimate the sedimentation coefficient for silica nanoparticles. The particle mass is $m_{\text{silica}} \approx 6 \text{ MDa}$ and the volume given by the diameter of 21 nm. For the surrounding liquid we use the solvent density of around 1.02 g/ml and likewise the solvent viscosity of 1 mPa s. Finally, as a hydrodynamic radius, the value for the hydrated condition of $R_{\text{silica}} = 15 \text{ nm}$ is used. The sedimentation coefficient turns out to be $s_{\text{silica}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ s}$ and the terminal velocity at $20\,000 \times g$ to 4 $\mu\text{m/s}$.

If the cell reaches a position in the gradient where its density matches the environment closer, its sedimentation velocity scales accordingly. For a difference of only 2 mg/ml, the velocity is 40 $\mu\text{m/s}$, accordingly. Based on these simple calculations, the time scale of RBC sedimentation in a self-forming Percoll gradient can be considered 10 to 100 times shorter compared to the time scale of the gradient formation process, that is defined by the underlying sedimentation of the silica nanoparticles.

6.10 Mass conservation of the density function

The conservation of mass requires the density function to meet Eqn. (4.22) at any time. The cross-sectional area was assumed to be a constant. For an arbitrary value of y we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\lambda/2-y}^{\lambda/2+y} \rho_P(h, t) dh \\
&= \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \right\} \int_{\lambda/2-y}^{\lambda/2+y} \left\{ \rho_{P,0} + \epsilon \log\left(\frac{\lambda}{h-h_0} - 1\right) \right\} dh + \rho_{P,0} \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \int_0^H dh \\
&= \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \right\} \left\{ \rho_{P,0} 2y + \int_{\lambda/2-y}^{\lambda/2+y} \epsilon \log\left(\frac{\lambda}{h-h_0} - 1\right) dh \right\} + \rho_{P,0} 2y \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \\
&= \rho_{P,0} 2y + \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \right\} \epsilon \int_{\lambda/2-y}^{\lambda/2+y} \log\left(\frac{\lambda}{h-h_0} - 1\right) dh
\end{aligned}$$

and furthermore

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\lambda/2-y}^{\lambda/2+y} \log\left(\frac{\lambda}{h-h_0} - 1\right) dh = \int_{-y}^y \log\left(\frac{\lambda}{h + \lambda/2 - h_0} - 1\right) dh \\
&= \int_{-y}^y \log\left(\frac{\lambda/2 - h_0 - h}{\lambda/2 - h_0 + h}\right) dh = \int_{-y}^y \log(\lambda/2 - h_0 - h) dh - \int_{-y}^y \log(\lambda/2 - h_0 + h) dh \\
&= \int_{-y}^y \log(\lambda/2 - h_0 - h) dh + \int_y^{-y} \log(\lambda/2 - h_0 - h) dh = 0
\end{aligned}$$

The integral vanishes as $\log\left(\frac{x_0 - x}{x_0 + x}\right)$ is odd in x . Therefore for $y = H/2$ and $\lambda = H$ it is

$$\int_0^H \rho_P(h, t) dh = \rho_{P,0} H \quad (6.15)$$

at any time. The immediate implication is $\langle \rho_P(h, t) \rangle_h = \rho_{P,0} \forall t$.

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Hiermit versichere ich an Eides statt, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Die aus anderen Quellen oder indirekt übernommenen Daten und Konzepte sind unter Angabe der Quelle gekennzeichnet. Die Arbeit wurde bisher weder im In- noch im Ausland in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form in einem Verfahren zur Erlangung eines akademischen Grades vorgelegt.

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